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D3.2 – Research ethics and integrity guidelines for R&I in the Green Transition

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Abbreviations

Table 1: List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full Term
ALLEA	All European Academies
DNSH	Do No Significant Harm
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
ECoC	European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
FFP	Fabrication, falsification, and plagiarism
RE&RI	Research Ethics and Research Integrity
REC	Research Ethics Committee
RE4GREEN	Research Ethics and Integrity for the GREEN Transition
R&I	Research and Innovation
SAB	Stakeholder Advisory Board
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the outputs of Task 3.2 of the RE4GREEN project, which focused on producing and adapting operational research ethics and research integrity (RE&RI) guidance that explicitly integrates environmental and climate considerations. Building on conceptual and empirical findings from WP1 and stakeholder insights from WP2, the task aimed to translate these findings into practical guidance that can be applied in diverse research and innovation contexts.

Rather than introducing new ethical frameworks, Task 3.2 adopts a complementary and integrative approach. Its outputs build on established structures such as the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ECoC), existing research ethics procedures, and the European Commission's forthcoming guidance on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm. The deliverable includes an Annex to the ECoC, as well as a set of stand-alone research ethics materials targeting researchers, research ethics committees (RECs), and citizen science contexts.

All materials emphasise feasibility and practical use in order to support ethical reflection and responsible research practice without increasing administrative burden or duplicating existing requirements. The outputs of Task 3.2 help strengthen the ethical governance of research and innovation in the context of the green transition, while remaining aligned with current European research integrity and ethics frameworks.

This deliverable brings together guidance materials developed for different audiences. Together, these materials function as a complementary guidance toolkit designed to support the consistent integration of environmental and climate considerations across research integrity, research ethics, and participatory research practices. While each document can be used independently, the set is designed to provide mutually reinforcing perspectives that address different roles within the research and innovation ecosystem. Readers may also focus on the sections most relevant to their role (e.g., researchers, research managers, members of research ethics committees, ethics and integrity experts, ethics appraisal experts, citizen scientists).

Table 2: Indicative mapping of target audiences to the guidance documents provided in this deliverable

Audience	Guidance materials
Researchers, research managers	RE4GREEN Annex to the ALLEA European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity Going Beyond Harm: A Starting Guide to Environmental & Climate Considerations in Research Ethics Engaging with Citizen Scientists: Integrating Environmental and Climate Considerations into Research Practice
Members of research ethics committees, ethics appraisal experts	RE4GREEN Annex to the ALLEA European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity Toward an Expanded Scope of Research Ethics Committees: Integrating Environmental and Climate Ethics

	Going Beyond Harm: A Starting Guide to Environmental & Climate Considerations in Research Ethics
Citizen scientists	Taking Part in Research: A Guide for Citizen Scientists on Environmental and Climate Considerations

Introduction

Environmental and climate challenges increasingly shape the context, aims, and impacts of research and innovation. At the same time, existing research ethics and integrity (RE&RI) frameworks have a limited capacity to address these considerations in a systematic and operational way. Research ethics procedures tend to focus primarily on human participants and immediate harms, while research integrity guidance rarely provides concrete direction on environmental and climate responsibilities. This gap creates uncertainty for researchers, research ethics committees (RECs), and institutions working in areas where research activities or outcomes interact with environmental systems, communities, and long-term sustainability goals.

Task 3.2 of the RE4GREEN project responds to this gap by developing practical guidance that integrates environmental and climate considerations into existing RE&RI structures. The task builds on the analytical work of WPI, which identified conceptual fragmentation and limited operationalisation of environmental and climate ethics within current guidance, and on stakeholder insights from WP2, which highlighted the need for feasible, institutionally supported solutions rather than additional high-level principles.

The materials presented in this deliverable reflect a deliberate methodological choice: to strengthen and adapt existing frameworks rather than create parallel ones. By aligning closely with the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ECoC), established ethics appraisal processes, and emerging EU-level guidance on environmental harm, Task 3.2 seeks to support responsible research practice that is both ethical and practically achievable. The deliverable brings together a set of complementary materials designed to be used independently or in combination, depending on the needs of different research actors.

Task 3.2

Overview

Task 3.2 focused on the production and/or adaptation of operational RE&RI guidelines to account for environmental and climate considerations. Building on the insights and gaps identified in WPI and on stakeholder insights generated through WP2, the task aimed to translate key concepts from environmental and climate ethics into practical guidance applicable across diverse R&I contexts. The task addresses a range of cross-cutting ethical and integrity issues relevant to research with environmental and climate implications, including the role of ethics and integrity experts, informed consent of individuals and communities, undue inducement and opt-out approaches, benefit-sharing arising from research, and the application of the precautionary approach across different R&I fields. Particular attention is paid to contexts where research interacts closely with communities and citizens. The outputs of Task 3.2 are primarily intended for researchers,

Research Ethics Committees (RECs), research managers, ethics and integrity experts, and Horizon Europe ethics appraisal experts, and also include dedicated guidance for citizen scientists and for researchers engaging with citizen science.

Background

The work of Task 3.2 was grounded in the findings of WPI, which demonstrated a clear and systematic gap in the integration of environmental and climate considerations within existing RE&RI resources. The mapping of environmental and climate ethics literature (RE4GREEN, 2025a and Bourban et al, 2026) showed that there is no stable or widely accepted operationalisation of environmental and climate ethics within RE&RI. Rather there is conceptual fragmentation, inconsistent terminology, and limited engagement between RE&RI and environmental and climate ethics. Complementing this, the gap analysis of RE&RI guidelines and frameworks (RE4GREEN, 2025b) revealed that most existing resources either make no reference to environmental or climate concerns or address them only superficially, typically through high-level principles such as sustainability or responsibility without providing actionable guidance. Justice-oriented concepts, environmental risk and precaution, community-level impacts, and the needs of disproportionately affected or Indigenous populations were found to be particularly underdeveloped.

Over the time Task 3.2 was carried out, the European Commission was also preparing the forthcoming Guidance Note on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm in EU-funded research. The Guidance Note focuses primarily on supporting applicants, beneficiaries, and ethics evaluators in identifying, assessing, and managing risks of environmental harm across the research lifecycle, particularly in the context of ethics self-assessment and ethics appraisal procedures. To ensure coherence and efficiency, Task 3.2 was deliberately designed not to replicate or reinterpret the Commission's work. Instead, the task adopted a complementary approach, recognising the Guidance Note as a key reference for assessment of environmental harm, while focusing its own efforts on the adaptation and operationalisation of RE&RI guidance more broadly. This allowed Task 3.2 to concentrate on ethical and integrity dimensions that extend beyond harm and risk assessment alone and to address how these considerations can be integrated into everyday research practice and governance structures. In this way, the outputs of Task 3.2 are intended to be used alongside the Commission Guidance Note, reinforcing rather than duplicating its role within the Horizon Europe ethics framework.

The methodological approach adopted in Task 3.2 was also informed by existing work on the development and operationalisation of ethics guidance for new and emerging domains, in particular the methods outlined in the SIENNA project's guidance on translating ethical analysis into operational instruments (SIENNA, 2023). These insights emphasise the importance of building on existing ethics frameworks and codes, combining general principle-based guidance with more practice-specific elaboration, and supporting the use of ethics guidelines through practical instruments and institutional processes. They also highlight the value of iterative, stepwise development processes involving expert input and stakeholder consultation, as well as the need to strengthen the role of RECs and institutions in overseeing ethically complex research areas. While drawing inspiration from these approaches, Task 3.2 adapted them to the specific objectives and scope of RE4GREEN. In particular, the methodology was tailored to address environmental and climate considerations within RE&RI, rather than focusing on a single technology domain. The approach was further shaped by the empirical findings of WPI and the stakeholder insights generated in WP2, and by the need to ensure complementarity with existing Horizon Europe ethics appraisal processes and the European Commission's forthcoming Guidance Note on environmental harms.

Interactions with Other WPs

This section outlines how Task 3.2 interacts with and builds upon the outputs of other work packages in the RE4GREEN project.

Figure 1: Task 3.2 interactions with other WPs

WP1 – Conceptual inputs and identified gaps

Task 3.2 built directly on the findings of WP1, which identified key gaps and needs in the integration of environmental and climate considerations within existing RE&RI literature, frameworks, and guidelines. As described above, WP1 highlighted the structural gap between environmental and climate ethics and RE&RI, the fragmented use of concepts, and the largely absent, abstract or superficial treatment of environmental and climate considerations in existing guidance. These insights informed both the scope and the methodological choices of Task 3.2.

WP2 – Social Lab (SL) insights and feedback

WP3 as a whole interlinked with WP2 through the provision of draft materials and discussion topics to the Social Labs (SLs). Insights generated through the SLs and workshops discussions played a central role in shaping the content and framing of the outputs of this task. Across the SLs, participants broadly supported the direction of WP3 but consistently emphasised challenges related to feasibility and practical implementation. A recurring insight was the need to avoid placing additional responsibilities on individual researchers and RECs alone. Instead, participants highlighted the importance of strengthening institutional responsibility and clarifying the roles of funders, research-performing organisations, publishers, and private-sector actors in supporting environmentally and climatically responsible research practices. RECs were widely viewed as already overburdened and in need of practical support rather than additional abstract requirements.

Participants in the SLs consistently emphasised that the RE&RI sector does not need additional high-level frameworks but rather practical tools that help stakeholders translate environmental and climate ethics into everyday decision-making. In response, Task 3.2 prioritised building on established structures, such as the ECoC (ALLEA, 2023), the forthcoming EU Guidance Note on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm in EU-funded research, and existing RE&RI procedures, by integrating environmental and climate considerations into them rather than creating parallel systems. The SLs also highlighted the need for concrete support for RECs, project teams, and researchers working with citizens. This led to the decision to develop targeted Task 3.2 outputs, including guidance for RECs, and practical resources for citizen-engaged research.

In addition to the inputs generated through WP2 SLs, the draft guidance developed under Task 3.2 was reviewed by a selected group of SL participants who expressed interest in engaging further with the development of the guidelines. Due to the parallel timelines of WP2 and WP3, it was not feasible to organise dedicated or formal validation workshops specifically for Task 3.2 outputs. Instead, an iterative review process was adopted, drawing on written feedback and targeted exchanges with interested SL participants. This approach enabled timely and focused input from stakeholders already familiar with the project's objectives and discussions. It also ensured continuity between the exploratory work of WP2 and the operational guidance produced in WP3. Feedback received through this process contributed to refining the clarity, relevance, and practical orientation of the guidance, particularly regarding feasibility, implementation contexts, and alignment with existing research governance structures.

WP4 – Training

Based on the guidance materials produced in Task 3.2, dedicated training micromodules have been developed for each of the guidance documents. These training resources are currently being integrated into [RE4GREEN's Embassy of Good Science](#) platform alongside other WP4 materials. The micromodules aim to support capacity building for researchers, ethics and integrity experts, RECs, and institutional actors by translating the guidance into accessible, practice-oriented educational formats.

WP5 – Communication and Dissemination

The guidance materials produced under Task 3.2 have been compiled into accessible PDF documents prepared in accordance with the RE4GREEN visual identity. These documents are provided in the Annex of this deliverable. The formats are intended to facilitate wider uptake, practical use, and reuse of the guidance by research institutions, RECs, and other stakeholders, supporting outreach activities aligned with RE4GREEN's broader dissemination strategy.

Methodology

The methodological approach adopted in Task 3.2 was shaped by four main factors:

- (i) the conceptual and empirical findings of WP1
- (ii) stakeholder insights generated through WP2 SLs
- (iii) the evolving policy landscape at EU level, including the preparation of the European Commission's Guidance Note on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm in EU-funded research
- (iv) existing work on operationalising ethics guidance in emerging domains, notably the SIENNA project's approach to translating ethical analysis into practical instruments.

Task 3.2 was methodologically grounded in an explicit distinction between RI and RE as two closely related but distinct domains. RI primarily concerns the professional responsibilities, standards of conduct, and norms governing good research practice, whereas RE focuses on the ethical evaluation of research activities, including risks, benefits, consent, justice, and the treatment of individuals, communities, and the environment. While the two domains overlap and are mutually reinforcing, they operate through different principles, practices, and governance mechanisms. Addressing environmental and climate considerations in research, therefore requires engagement with both.

This distinction is also reflected in the existing European governance landscape. RI benefits from a well-established and widely accepted framework in the form of the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ECoC), whereas RE lacks an equivalent, unified European framework. Instead, RE is primarily operationalised through the ethics appraisal procedure (EAP) and the work of RECs at the institutional and project level.

On this basis, Task 3.2 adopted a two-workstream methodology, with one workstream dedicated to RI and one to RE.

RI Workstream

For the RI workstream, the ECoC was treated as the established baseline framework. Task 3.2 deliberately avoided revising, replacing, or competing with the ECoC. Instead, it sought to complement it by building on clauses within the Code that explicitly recognise that ecosystems, cultural heritage, and the environment form part of what must be respected in research practice. The methodological choice was therefore to produce an Annex to the ECoC that interprets its four core principles (reliability, honesty, respect, and accountability) through an environmental and climate lens. This approach allows environmental and climate considerations to be embedded within existing integrity standards and practices across disciplines and institutions, while preserving the authority and coherence of the ECoC as the central European framework for research integrity.

RE Workstream

For the RE workstream, Task 3.2 focused on developing practical tools and guidance to support ethical reflection and decision-making within existing ethics processes. Unlike research integrity, RE lacks a shared European code; therefore, the task did not aim to create a new overarching framework, but to align its outputs with the structures most commonly used in practice. Thus the task addressed areas where additional ethical guidance is needed to support the assessment and governance of research with environmental and climate implications. In this context, Task 3.2 produced a set of complementary guidance documents addressing different actors and research settings. These include:

- a starting guide that complements the Commission's Guidance Note by going beyond harm-based assessment to support broader ethical reflection on environmental and climate considerations
- guidance for RECs, designed to support ethics review without increasing administrative burden, and to help RECs assess environmental and climate considerations
- guidance for researchers engaging with citizen scientists, addressing consent, participation, benefit-sharing, and power relations in citizen-engaged research
- a guide for citizen scientists, written in accessible language, clarifying rights, responsibilities, and environmental and climate considerations when participating in research.

In practical terms, the guidance materials developed under Task 3.2 were produced through an iterative and collaborative process that prioritised operationalisation throughout. The requirements set out in the task description were first analysed to define the scope and objectives of the task, alongside a review of the existing RE&RI landscape, which informed the overall methodological approach. Responsibilities for leading specific aspects of the task were allocated across consortium partners according to their expertise, with, for example, ECSA leading contributions related to citizen science and participatory research, and EUREC leading work related to RECs and ethics review practices. While specific partners led different components, all task partners contributed to the development of the materials through progressive drafting, review, and revision. Multiple iterations of the documents were produced, with feedback integrated not only from within the consortium but also from external stakeholders, including members of the Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB) and participants in the project's SLs. Across both the RI and RE workstreams, Task 3.2 deliberately avoided proposing new high-level ethical frameworks, instead focusing on adapting and extending existing structures, providing context-sensitive guidance, and supporting practical use by researchers, RECs, and institutions. The outputs of Task 3.2 are therefore designed to be used alongside existing ethics requirements, including the forthcoming European Commission Guidance Note.

Materials Produced

The materials presented in this section are written as stand-alone documents. They are intended to be read and used independently by different audiences, who may engage with only one guidance rather than the full set of Task 3.2 outputs. For this reason, some concepts, explanations, and contextual information may appear more than once across the materials. This repetition is intentional and aims to ensure that each document provides readers with the necessary context and guidance without requiring them to consult the other outputs of this deliverable.

Research Integrity

This Annex builds directly on the ECoC and is meant to complement it, not to revise or replace it. To keep the guidance clear and easy to use, the Annex follows the same structure as the ECoC, covering its principles, good research practices, and violations of research integrity. Where helpful, short quotations from the ECoC are included. The Annex was reviewed by Maura Hiney, a member of the RE4GREEN Stakeholder Advisory Board who was involved in drafting the original ECoC (2017 and 2023). The feedback from this review was very positive and confirmed that the Annex remains faithful to the spirit and intent of the Code while strengthening its relevance for environmental and climate-related research.

RE4GREEN Annex to the ALLEA European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity

Preamble

Research plays a crucial role in shaping the pathways through which societies confront pressing global challenges, including climate change, biodiversity loss, pollution, and other forms of environmental degradation. At the same time, research, like all human activities, can leave environmental and social footprints, both through its practices and through the applications it enables. These impacts are not inherent to research but can arise unintentionally or out of a lack of considerations for these impacts. Therefore, strengthening integrity in the context of environmental and climate concerns requires supporting practices that responsibly account for and minimise such impacts. Research that aims to serve the public good must uphold high standards of rigour, transparency, and responsibility while avoiding actions that may contribute to environmental or social harm.

The [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity \(ECoC\)](#) (ALLEA, 2023) sets out the foundational principles of **reliability**, **honesty**, **respect**, and **accountability**. These principles remain central to all research activities within the European Research Area and beyond. The ECoC recognises in its 2017 revision (ALLEA, 2017) that ecosystems, cultural heritage, and the environment are aspects that must be respected in research practice. However, as environmental and climate concerns become increasingly urgent, there is a need for additional guidance that translates these broad principles into operational responsibilities for the research community.

In parallel, the European Union has established the principle of **Do No Significant Harm (DNSH)** within its regulatory framework under the EU Taxonomy Regulation (EU, 2020). This ensures that publicly funded activities do not undermine key environmental objectives such as climate change mitigation and adaptation, biodiversity protection, or pollution prevention. While DNSH provides an important legal benchmark, it is narrowly defined and primarily tailored to investment and economic activities. Recognising this limitation, the European Commission will soon be issuing dedicated guidance for research, offering a broader and more

flexible framework for identifying, assessing, and mitigating environmental harms throughout the research lifecycle. This guidance extends beyond DNSH by addressing a wider range of environmental ethics considerations, including research topics, methods, practices and new ethics requirements. Together, these developments emphasise the need to embed environmental and climate considerations at the heart of research integrity and practice.

This Annex is intended to complement the ECoC. It offers interpretive guidance on how the existing principles and practices of the ECoC should be understood and applied through an environmental and climate lens. These interpretations remain fully compatible with the freedom of research and do not restrict the independence with which researchers formulate questions and pursue knowledge. Following the structure of the ECoC, this Annex is organised into three sections: Principles, Good Research Practices, and Violations of Research Integrity. Each section provides insights on how environmental and climate considerations can be integrated into established research integrity standards.

Principles

The principles of the ECoC remain the foundation for responsible research. This Annex does not revise or add to these principles. Instead, it clarifies how their meaning extends to the environmental and climate dimensions of research, particularly where research activities or outcomes have the potential to affect ecosystems, natural resources, or the conditions that support human and non-human life. The aim is to support the research community in interpreting the four ECoC principles in ways that reflect contemporary environmental and climate considerations.

Reliability

“Reliability in ensuring the quality of research, reflected in the design, methodology, analysis, and use of resources.”

Reliability requires rigorous, well-designed, and methodologically sound research. From an environmental and climate perspective, it includes generating accurate, valid, and reproducible assessments of potential environmental implications of the research. This involves ensuring that environmental assumptions, uncertainties, and real-world feasibility considerations are accounted for in research design and execution, so that findings remain dependable and applicable in practice.

Honesty

“Honesty in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting, and communicating research in a transparent, fair, full, and unbiased way.”

Honesty requires transparency on the environmental dimensions of research, including potential benefits, harms, limitations and uncertainties. It includes avoiding misrepresentation, such as overstating environmental benefits or concealing or downplaying uncertainties and potential harms and ensuring that all claims related to environmental performance or sustainability are supported by evidence and presented without exaggeration.

Respect

“Respect for colleagues, research participants, research subjects, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage, and the environment.”

Respect, as recognised in the ECoC, extends to ecosystems, cultural heritage, and the environment. Interpreted in an environmental and climate context, respect entails recognising the interdependence of human and natural systems, and the moral significance of non-human life. It includes attentiveness to how research activities or outcomes impact those most affected by environmental degradation, including Indigenous peoples, local communities, and future generations. It also involves acknowledging and engaging with relevant knowledge systems, including local, traditional, and indigenous knowledge, where appropriate.

Accountability

“Accountability for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision, and mentoring, and for its wider societal impacts.”

Accountability includes responsibility for the environmental implications of research processes and outcomes. This entails careful stewardship of resources, adherence to applicable environmental obligations, and transparency toward institutions, funders, and society about environmental considerations relevant to the research. Accountability also requires monitoring and reflecting on the broader consequences that research may have for environmental and climate objectives and establishing mitigation measures when these are assessed as being harmful.

Good Research Practices

Research Environment

- Research institutions should foster a culture that acknowledges and accounts for the environmental implications of research activities and outcomes and supports responsible resource use.
- Policies on good research practice should include clear expectations for environmentally responsible conduct, consistent with applicable environmental obligations.
- Institutions should ensure that environmental considerations are not undermined by unrealistic performance pressures or incentives.
- Where research involves environmental or climate data, institutions should provide appropriate infrastructure to support its proper documentation, stewardship, and traceability.

Training, Supervision, and Mentoring

- Training in research design and methodology should, where relevant, include awareness of the environmental or climate implications of research choices.
- Ethics and integrity training should familiarise researchers with applicable environmental obligations and emerging requirements.
- Supervisors should model environmentally responsible research behaviour and support researchers in recognising when environmental considerations require specialist input.

Research Procedures

- When developing research ideas, researchers should consider whether their work may have environmental or climate impacts and seek appropriate expertise when uncertain.
- Careful and well-considered research design should include reflection on the environmental footprint of methods—such as energy use, material consumption, travel, fieldwork, or laboratory practices—and consider lower-impact equivalents where possible.
- Transparent reporting should include, where applicable, environmental assumptions, uncertainties, or contextual factors that influence the interpretation of findings.

Safeguards

- Compliance with codes, guidelines, and regulations should include meeting relevant environmental requirements, such as those relating to pollution prevention, biodiversity protection, or responsible fieldwork.
- Research involving environmental or biological subjects should seek to avoid unnecessary disturbance to ecosystems, habitats, and natural resources by following established protocols for minimising harm.
- Assessing potential harms should include identifying foreseeable environmental risks associated with the research and taking proportionate steps to avoid, minimise, or mitigate them.
- In projects involving public or community participation, environmental practices should be safe and responsible and communicated clearly.

Data Practices and Management

- Stewardship of environmental or climate-related data should ensure clear documentation, secure storage, and preservation sufficient to support reproducibility and long-term value.
- Open access to environmental data should follow FAIR principles while respecting restrictions on sensitive ecological information or community-held knowledge.
- Researchers should respect applicable rights and expectations when using community-generated environmental data, including conditions on sharing, reuse, or disclosure.

Collaborative Working

- Collaboration agreements should clarify environmental responsibilities, including how potential environmental impacts will be assessed, communicated, and addressed.
- Where collaborations involve local communities or indigenous groups connected to the environments or resources affected by the research, expectations regarding community consent, indigenous data sovereignty, and the right to decline participation should be explicitly agreed upon.
- Partners should consider the fair distribution of environmental benefits and burdens, particularly where research outcomes may disproportionately affect vulnerable or marginalised groups.

Publication, Dissemination, and Authorship

- Claims about environmental impacts, benefits, or sustainability should be accurate, evidence-based, and presented without exaggeration or misrepresentation.
- Transparency in publication should include, where relevant, assumptions about environmental conditions or impacts underlying the research, limitations, uncertainties, or contextual factors that affect interpretation or policy relevance.

- Acknowledgements should accurately reflect contributions from environmental data sources, field sites, or community-generated knowledge in line with prior agreements.
- Corrections or retractions should be issued promptly when environmental claims or assessments are found to be inaccurate or misleading.

Reviewing and Assessment

- Reviewers should ensure that environmental or climate-related claims are supported by appropriate evidence and that uncertainties are clearly acknowledged.
- Assessment of research project submissions involving environmental dimensions should consider the robustness of environmental methodologies, data, and assumptions.
- Editors should be alert to conflicts of interest where reviewers have ties to industries or activities with significant environmental stakes that may bias their assessment (e.g. fossil fuels, industrial agriculture, resource extraction), and should have appropriate policies in place to identify, disclose, and manage such conflicts, including measures such as transparency requirements, replacing reviewers where necessary, or declining to publish work where conflicts cannot be adequately addressed.
- Confidentiality obligations should extend to sensitive environmental information, such as locations of endangered species or community-held environmental knowledge, where disclosure could cause harm.

Violations of Research Integrity

Research Misconduct and other Unacceptable Practices

Fabrication, falsification, and plagiarism (FFP) are fundamental violations of research integrity. When research has environmental or climate relevance, these forms of misconduct may result in inappropriate environmental decisions or policies, or obscure potential harms. Beyond FFP, breaches of good research practice include activities that distort the research record or undermine the integrity of the research process, for example through misleading reporting, inappropriate influence, misuse of data, or harmful disclosure practices. In an environmental and climate context, these may include, but are not confined to:

- Misrepresenting or exaggerating environmental benefits, sustainability claims, or climate impacts ("greenwashing"), including withholding information regarding relevant uncertainties or limitations.
- Selectively reporting environmental results in ways that mislead stakeholders, policymakers, or affected communities.
- Suppressing or failing to disclose environmental data, especially when such omission could hide potential risks, harms, or negative findings.
- Allowing funders or sponsors with environmental interests (e.g., industrial, political, or commercial stakeholders) to influence the independence or impartiality of the research or its reporting.
- Misusing environmental or community-generated data in ways that breach agreed conditions of use, ownership, or consent.
- Disclosing sensitive environmental information (such as the location of endangered species or fragile ecosystems) where such disclosure could cause harm.
- Accusing others of environmental misconduct or harm in a malicious or unsubstantiated way.

Serious forms of such practices may be sanctionable. All require prevention and correction through training, supervision, and a supportive research environment.

Dealing with Violations and Allegations of Misconduct

The principles for handling allegations of research misconduct apply equally to cases involving environmental or climate-relevant research. Investigations should be fair, consistent, confidential, and transparent, and should avoid conflicts of interest, including those arising from financial, organisational, or commercial interests and interests linked to environmentally relevant research outcomes. Processes should protect the rights of all parties involved, including bona fide whistle-blowers who may raise concerns about environmental risks, misrepresentation of environmental impacts, or unethical use of environmental or community data. Investigations should consider whether institutional structures, pressures, or incentives contributed to the breach, and should ensure that appropriate restorative or corrective action is taken when allegations are upheld or dismissed.

Key resources

1. ALLEA | All European Academies. (2023). The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity – Revised Edition 2023. ALLEA. <https://doi.org/10.26356/ECOC>
2. ALLEA | All European Academies. (2017). The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity – Revised Edition 2023. ALLEA. <https://www.allea.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/ALLEA-European-Code-of-Conduct-for-Research-Integrity-2017.pdf>
3. EU | European Union (2020). Regulation (EU) 2020/852 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 June 2020 on the establishment of a framework to facilitate sustainable investment, and amending Regulation (EU) 2019/2088. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32020R0852>

Research Ethics

The Research Ethics materials developed under Task 3.2 support ethical reflection and decision-making in research that incorporates environmental and climate considerations. They are designed to complement existing ethics procedures and requirements, particularly the forthcoming European Commission's Guidance Note on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm, by addressing ethical questions that extend beyond harm-based assessment alone. Together, these materials aim to support researchers, ethics committees, and participants in identifying, reflecting on, and responsibly addressing environmental and climate-related ethical issues across different research contexts.

Going Beyond Harm: A Starting Guide to Environmental & Climate Considerations in Research Ethics

Executive Summary

This starting guide supports the integration of environmental and climate considerations into research ethics practice beyond harm-based assessment. It is intended for researchers, research teams, research ethics committees (RECs), evaluators, and project coordinators involved in the design, conduct, and review of research.

While existing ethics frameworks primarily focus on the identification and prevention of harm (particularly risks to human participants) research activities may raise ethically relevant environmental and climate considerations even where no significant environmental harm is expected. These considerations include questions of responsibility, precaution, justice, fairness, participation, and the longer-term implications of research assumptions, methods, and outputs. This guide complements, but does not replace, the European Commission's forthcoming Guidance Note on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm in EU-funded research. Rather than introducing prescriptive rules, it adopts a reflective and context-sensitive approach based on guiding questions and illustrative examples.

The guidance is structured around three complementary dimensions of environmentally and climate-responsible research:

- **Responsible and precautionary research:** encouraging reflection on research design, assumptions, methodological choices, and transparency
- **Just and fair research:** addressing the distribution of benefits, burdens, risks, and intergenerational implications
- **Participatory and inclusive research:** focusing on inclusion, pluralism, and recognition of diverse knowledge systems

The core message of this guide is that environmental and climate considerations are not limited to risk mitigation. Ethical reflection may also be warranted in relation to how research frames problems, shapes decision-making, and influences societal and environmental trajectories. The guide is designed for flexible use across disciplines and research contexts, supporting ethical reflection, documentation, and discussion within research teams and ethics review processes.

HOW TO USE THIS GUIDE (IN 3 STEPS)

1. **Screen for harms first**

Use the forthcoming **EC Guidance Note** on assessing and managing environmental harms to identify and mitigate potential harms linked to your research topic, methods, and practices. This process may be complemented by structured tools, such as the **RE4GREEN Risk Assessment Tool** (RE4GREEN, 2026), to support systematic reflection on environmental and climate-related risks.

2. **Then go beyond harm**

Use this guide to reflect on responsibility and precaution, justice and fairness, and participation and inclusion, including ethical issues that may still be relevant even when significant environmental harm is unlikely.

3. **Record your choices**

Document what you decided, why these decisions were taken, and how you will monitor and revise your approach over time (e.g. in ethics materials, project governance, and communication with stakeholders).

Introduction

Environmental and climate considerations are increasingly recognised as integral to responsible research practice. However, as recent research has highlighted, there is a structural gap in the current ethics landscape (Bourban, 2026) and governance (RE4GREEN, 2025). Existing Research Ethics (RE) literature and frameworks focus primarily on human participants and the ethical acceptability of research involving them, while environmental and climate ethics focus on ecological systems, justice, and sustainability. The two domains rarely intersect. As a result, researchers often lack clear ethical foundations for understanding how their work may engage environmental or climate responsibilities such as questions of responsibility, environmental and climate justice, or long-term environmental implications. The European Commission's (EC) forthcoming Guidance Note on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm in EU-funded research represents an important development bridging this gap. It offers a clear and practical framework to help applicants, researchers, and ethics evaluators identify, assess, and manage potential environmental harms within EU-funded research. This guide builds on and complements that work.

Environmental and climate considerations in RE extend beyond questions of harm. Research activities can raise ethical concerns even when no significant environmental harm is expected, such as when research assumptions, models, or design choices may influence long-term environmental or societal trajectories. This starting guide aims to embed key ethical considerations that are not always captured by harm-based assessments alone into RE practice, helping researchers and evaluators identify relevant environmental and climate considerations during project design, execution and evaluation. It does so by structuring the guidance around three complementary dimensions of environmentally and climate-responsible research.

Given the diversity of research domains, methods, and contexts, it is not possible to define a single set of actions that would be appropriate in all cases. For this reason, the guide adopts a reflective approach based on guiding questions and illustrative examples, rather than prescriptive rules. This approach is intended to support context-sensitive ethical reflection, enabling researchers and evaluators to identify relevant environmental and climate considerations in light of their specific research activities.

This guide does not replace the Commission's Guidance Note on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm and it is not intended to serve as a risk-assessment tool.

Responsible and precautionary research

This section focuses on how research can be designed and conducted in in contexts where research activities may have environmental or climate relevance, particularly where activities are complex, uncertain, or potentially far-reaching in their effects. The expectations outlined in the EC's Guidance Note on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm, such as avoiding unnecessary harm, considering less harmful alternatives, and ensuring that research topics, methods, and practices are not likely to generate significant harm are foundational to ethical research.

Extending beyond harm avoidance, this section supports reflection on how research choices, methods, and assumptions interact with broader environmental and climate dynamics. It invites the reader to consider not only whether harm is likely to occur, but also how research practices may reinforce particular pathways, norms, or dependencies in contexts characterised by complexity and uncertainty.

1. Integrate environmental and climate considerations into everyday research governance¹

Questions to consider:

- How are environmental and climate reflections included in team discussions, planning or documentation?
- How do our procurement, data management, or infrastructure decisions consider environmental or climate relevance, even when these are not the primary focus of the research?
- How is responsibility for raising and documenting environmental and climate considerations clearly understood within the research team?

Example:

A consortium adds a short environmental reflection item to its regular meeting agenda, ensuring that environmental considerations become part of ongoing decision-making rather than a one-off consideration.

2. Reflect on the assumptions embedded in your research

Questions to consider:

- What do I assume to be necessary, normal, or unavoidable in my research?
- Do these assumptions reinforce patterns that could have environmental or climate implications?
- Could alternative approaches challenge or unsettle these assumptions?

Example:

A public health research project on heatwave prevention relies mainly on data collected through smartphone apps, thus assuming that everyone has a smartphone. Reflecting on this assumption may reveal that people with limited digital access are underrepresented in the dataset, including groups living in poorly insulated housing or in urban areas with higher heat exposure. As a result, certain forms of climate-related environmental vulnerability may be insufficiently captured in the evidence base used to understand heat risk

¹ This dimension focuses on research governance at the project and team level, including the responsibilities of individual researchers, project consortia, and relevant organisational units.

and inform adaptation measures. This raises ethical questions about how research assumptions shape which climate impacts, environments, and populations are made visible in research and which ones remain overlooked.

3. Consider your sphere of influence, not only your direct impacts

Questions to consider:

- Could my method, dataset or workflow become a template that others follow?
- Might my work normalise certain approaches in the field?
- Could downstream use of my outputs have environmental or climate implications beyond this project that I have not yet considered?

Example:

A research project develops a model to compare cities or regions for policy or investment purposes based primarily on economic performance indicators, without integrating environmental or climate-related factors. While this may reflect methodological or data limitations, the model's influence may extend beyond the project itself if it is reused by policymakers, consultants, or other researchers. In such cases, the model can contribute to decision-making frameworks that systematically prioritise economic metrics while downplaying climate risks such as heat exposure, environmental quality, or climate resilience. Reflecting on the project's sphere of influence highlights the ethical responsibility to consider how research outputs may shape environmentally relevant decisions and priorities beyond their original research context.

4. Practice transparency

Questions to consider:

- What trade-offs shaped my methodological choices (e.g., convenience vs. efficiency)?
- Were environmentally preferable alternatives considered?
- Can I briefly explain why certain options were selected?

Example:

A research team models future economic trends while holding environmental and climate conditions constant for the sake of analytical simplicity. While such simplifications are common in research, practising transparency involves explicitly stating this assumption and explaining its implications. In particular, users of the research should be able to understand that the projections do not account for factors such as climate impacts, environmental degradation, or resource constraints that could affect economic feasibility or long-term sustainability. Making these limitations explicit supports responsible use of the results in contexts where environmental and climate conditions are likely to influence outcomes.

Just and fair research

This section focuses on questions of fairness that arise from how research and innovation affect people, communities, and future generations. It addresses how benefits, burdens, risks, and opportunities associated

with research are distributed, and how these effects may vary across social, geographic, and temporal contexts. The guidance uses selected justice perspectives as practical lenses to support ethical reflection.

1. Consider how benefits and burdens are distributed (distributive justice)

Questions to consider:

- What kinds of benefits, opportunities, or advantages may arise from this research (scientific, societal, economic, environmental)?
- Who is likely to benefit from the knowledge, technologies, or outcomes produced by this research?
- Who may bear costs, limitations, or unintended consequences associated with the research or its outcomes?
- Who owns, controls, and can access the data and the outputs of the research? Does the project respect community or Indigenous data governance where relevant (including conditions for sharing and reuse)? (e.g., [CARE principles](#) for Indigenous data governance)

Example:

A research project uses environmental or socio-economic data collected in low- and middle-income countries. However, most of the research benefits, such as high-impact publications, follow-on funding, or agenda-setting influence, accrue to institutions based in the Global North. Reflecting on this distribution highlights potential imbalances between those who contribute data or local knowledge and those who primarily benefit from the research outputs.

2. Consider impacts across generations (intergenerational justice)

Questions to consider:

- How might this research affect future generations, even if impacts are not immediate?
- Does the research contribute to pathways that limit future options or create long-term dependencies?
- How are we weighing short-term benefits against potential long-term environmental or societal consequences?

Example:

A research project prioritises short-term efficiency gains through the rapid deployment of a technology without considering its long-term resource demands or disposal implications. Reflecting on intergenerational justice highlights whether alternative approaches could better preserve options and resources for future generations.

3. Attend to historical and structural inequalities (restorative justice)

Questions to consider:

- Does this research take place in contexts shaped by past injustices, extractive practices², or long-standing inequalities, e.g. in formerly colonised countries?
- Could the research unintentionally reproduce or reinforce these patterns?
- Are there opportunities for us to acknowledge past harms, support repair, or ensure reciprocity in research relationships?

Example:

A research project is conducted in a region that has historically been subject to extractive research practices, where data and resources were taken without clear benefits for local communities. Reflecting on restorative justice invites consideration of how the project can engage more respectfully, acknowledge this history, and explore forms of reciprocity or benefit-sharing.

Participatory and inclusive research

Research engages diverse social contexts, values, and forms of knowledge. Ethical reflection, therefore, extends beyond outcomes to questions of who participates in research and decision-making as well as whose knowledge is treated as legitimate. Where research has environmental or climate implications, these questions are particularly important because research may affect shared environments, local practices, and long-term societal and environmental trajectories. This section focuses on participation, pluralism, inclusion and respecting multiple epistemologies as dimensions of responsible research practice, particularly where research affects communities, relies on local knowledge, or informs societal decisions. Participation is meaningful when contributors can influence research questions, the interpretation of findings, or the use of results, rather than being limited to data provision alone.

1. Reflect on who is included in decision-making (procedural justice)

Questions to consider:

- Who is involved in defining research questions, methods, or priorities?
- Are we meaningfully consulting affected groups and individuals during the design and implementation of the research?
- Are participation processes designed so that they enable affected groups to realistically take part?

Example:

A consortium designs an environmental monitoring study without consulting local communities. Procedural justice invites reflection on whether earlier or more systematic engagement could improve both inclusiveness and research quality.

2. Recognise whose knowledge and perspectives are valued (epistemic and recognitional justice)

Questions to consider:

² Extractive research practices refer to approaches in which data, knowledge, or resources are primarily collected from individuals or communities without meaningful participation, transparency, recognition, or fair sharing of benefits arising from the research.

- Whose knowledge is treated as legitimate in this research?
- Are we prioritising certain forms of knowledge, experience, or expertise over others?
- Are we systematically undervaluing certain perspectives or experiences or treating them as less credible?
- Are the perspectives, values, or practices of affected groups acknowledged and respected?
- Are all contributions to the research process appropriately credited?

Example:

A climate adaptation project relies exclusively on technical models developed by external experts, while local or experiential knowledge is not considered relevant to the research. Reflecting on epistemic and recognition justice highlights whether important insights are being overlooked and whether some perspectives are implicitly treated as less credible or valuable.

3. Reflect on how people are involved in the conduct of research

Questions to consider:

- Are we involving participants in research activities that relate directly to environmental or climate conditions in their local context (e.g., observations, monitoring, interpretation of change)?
- Do participatory roles allow contributors to share context-specific environmental knowledge, lived experience, or observations that may not be captured through technical data alone?
- Are we informing participants about how their contributions relate to environmental or climate questions addressed by the research, including how data will be used, shared (e.g., as open data where applicable, or generalised/withheld where precise information could cause environmental harm), and interpreted?
- Are appropriate support, feedback, or training provided to enable meaningful participation in environmentally or climate-relevant research activities?

Example:

A project collects environmental observations through a citizen science platform but limits participant involvement to data submission, without explaining how observations contribute to understanding local environmental change. Reflecting on participation in practice highlights whether participants could be more meaningfully engaged through feedback, shared interpretation of results, or contextual discussion of environmental trends.

Conclusion

This starting guide provides a structured entry point for reflecting on environmental and climate considerations in research ethics beyond the identification and management of harm. By focusing on responsible and precautionary research practice, fairness of impacts across society and generations, and participation and pluralism in research and decision-making, the guide supports early-stage ethical reflection during project design and evaluation. This guide is intended to complement existing ethics procedures and the EC's guidance on environmental harm, not to replace formal risk assessment or ethical review. Its questions and examples are designed to be used flexibly, supporting discussion within research teams, RECs, and evaluation processes.

Applying these considerations in practice also depends on appropriate awareness and capacity among researchers, ethics reviewers, and evaluators. Environmental and climate ethics are evolving fields, and continuous learning is essential to ensure that ethical reflection keeps pace with scientific, technological, and societal developments. The process and outcomes of ethical reflection may be further strengthened where researchers and reviewers engage with relevant guidance and training materials through preparatory or practice-oriented activities. To support such capacity-building, RE4GREEN has developed a set of training materials on environmental and climate ethics, which are openly available through the [Embassy of Good Science](#).

Further Reading

1. RE4GREEN (2026). Recommendations on environmental and climate ethics amendment of risk assessment strategies. Deliverable D3.2, RE4GREEN project, Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement No. 101131706.
2. Bourban, M., Lenzi, D., Sørensen, M. et al. Convergences and Gaps between Environmental Ethics, Climate Ethics, and Research Ethics: A Scoping Review. *Sci Eng Ethics* (2026). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-025-00575-8>
3. RE4GREEN (2025). Gap analysis of research ethics and integrity resources for R&I in general and new climate and environmental technologies in particular. Deliverable D1.3, RE4GREEN project, Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement No. 101131706.

Toward an Expanded Scope of Research Ethics Committees: Integrating Environmental and Climate Ethics

Executive Summary

This guidance supports Research Ethics Committees (RECs) in integrating environmental and climate considerations into existing ethics review practices. It is intended primarily for REC members, ethics reviewers, ethics administrators, and institutional actors involved in research governance, while also being relevant to researchers and evaluators interacting with ethics review processes.

Environmental degradation, climate change, and biodiversity loss are increasingly recognised within European and international research ethics frameworks as ethically relevant concerns. However, existing REC mandates, expertise, and review tools were largely developed in response to biomedical and human-subject research and are not always structured to systematically address environmental or climate-related ethical issues. Rather than introducing new ethical principles, responsibilities, or procedural layers, this guidance adopts a supportive and proportionate approach. From the RE4GREEN perspective, "expanding the scope" of RECs refers to strengthening the capacity of ethics review to address environmental and climate considerations that are already embedded within contemporary research ethics and governance frameworks.

To support practical implementation, the guidance provides:

- Conceptual framing of the evolving role of RECs in relation to environmental and climate ethics
- Analysis of structural gaps and challenges in current ethics review practice
- A voluntary and illustrative Environmental & Climate Ethics Review Reflection Tool
- A curated set of existing resources relevant to REC practice

This guidance is designed to complement, and operate alongside, existing ethics appraisal procedures and the forthcoming Guidance Note on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm in EU-funded research by the European Commission.

Background & Evolution of RECs

Research Ethics Committees (RECs) were originally established to protect the rights, dignity, and well-being of human participants, particularly within medical and health-related research. Their core procedures and review practices developed in response to concrete risks associated with biomedical experimentation, with a primary focus on informed consent, the proportionality of risks and benefits, and the protection of vulnerable individuals.

Over time, ethical review in research has broadened beyond individual participants to include animals, communities, and society at large, reflecting growing awareness of the social, distributive, and long-term impacts of research activities. In parallel, environmental degradation, climate change, and biodiversity loss have increasingly been recognised as factors that shape human well-being and societal resilience. Environmental and climate ethics have therefore emerged as a relevant extension of contemporary research ethics, grounded in the interdependence of human and ecological systems.

The institutionalisation of ethics review has, however, developed unevenly across disciplines and national contexts. While RECs are firmly established in biomedical research and in parts of the social sciences, this is not the case across all research domains. In many technical disciplines, engineering fields, and parts of the environmental sciences (especially where research does not involve direct interaction with human participants) formal institutional REC structures are weakly institutionalised or absent. Even where RECs exist, their review practices do not always systematically address environmental or climate considerations.

As a result, research activities with potential environmental or climate impacts often fall outside established ethics review practices despite their ethical relevance. Findings from RE4GREEN Deliverable D1.3³ confirm that existing research ethics and integrity guidance largely treats environmental considerations peripherally, and that training resources for ethics reviewers rarely address environmental or climate ethics in a structured way.

These developments highlight a gradual expansion of ethical expectations in research, alongside persistent gaps in how environmental and climate considerations are reflected in ethics review practice. This underlines the need for clear, proportionate, and supportive guidance that helps RECs integrate such considerations into existing review processes, without altering their core role or increasing administrative burden.

Normative Shift: The Environment in European and International Research Ethics Frameworks

European and international research ethics frameworks increasingly recognise environmental protection and sustainability as integral components of responsible research conduct. This reflects a broader understanding that environmental degradation, climate change, and biodiversity loss are not external to research ethics, but are closely connected to human well-being, societal resilience, and justice.

At the European level, the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity⁴ explicitly includes respect for the environment and ecosystems as part of responsible research practice across disciplines. Similarly, the revised Declaration of Helsinki (2024)⁵ introduces an explicit requirement for medical research to be designed and conducted in ways that avoid or minimise environmental harm and promote ecological sustainability. While the Declaration of Helsinki is specific to medical research, it reflects a wider normative shift that links environmental harm to ethical responsibilities such as risk–benefit assessment, responsibility, and justice.

Within the EU research governance framework, this normative shift is further operationalised through Horizon Europe ethics requirements and the application of the Do No Significant Harm (DNSH) principle. The forthcoming European Commission Guidance Note on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm in EU-funded research provides practical support for applicants, beneficiaries, and ethics evaluators in identifying, assessing, and mitigating environmental risks across the research lifecycle. By explicitly linking environmental harm to established ethical principles such as scientific quality, social value, justice, and

³ RE4GREEN (2025). Gap analysis of research ethics and integrity resources for R&I in general and new climate and environmental technologies in particular. Deliverable D1.3, RE4GREEN project, Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement No. 101131706.

⁴ ALLEA | All European Academies. (2023). The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity – Revised Edition 2023. ALLEA. <https://doi.org/10.26356/ECOC>

⁵ World Medical Association. World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki: Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Participants. JAMA. 2025;333(1):71–74. doi:10.1001/jama.2024.21972

proportionality, the Guidance Note confirms that environmental and climate considerations form part of ethical appraisal rather than a separate or optional concern.

Taken together, these developments indicate that environmental and climate ethics are already embedded within the normative foundations of European and international research ethics. The challenge for ethics review is therefore not to introduce new ethical principles, but to support the consistent and proportionate integration of these existing expectations into ethics review practice, in ways that are feasible across diverse research contexts.

From Ethical Expectations to Ethics Review Practice: Gaps and Challenges for RECs

European research ethics policy increasingly recognises environmental and climate considerations as ethically relevant. Horizon Europe ethics requirements⁶, the application of the Do No Significant Harm (DNSH) principle, and the forthcoming European Commission Guidance Note all confirm that potential environmental harms should be identified and addressed as part of ethical appraisal. In practice, however, these expectations are not yet consistently reflected in ethics review processes.

This gap is partly rooted in the historical development of RECs. REC mandates, expertise, and review tools were largely shaped in response to biomedical research and research involving direct human participation. As a result, ethics review frameworks are generally better equipped to assess immediate and individual-level risks rather than indirect, cumulative, long-term, or environmentally mediated impacts. Environmental and climate considerations may therefore be addressed unevenly or implicitly treated as falling outside the core scope of ethics review.

These challenges are particularly visible in research involving complex infrastructures, advanced technologies, or data-intensive methods, such as the use of artificial intelligence, where environmental impacts may arise from energy use, resource consumption, or downstream effects. They also arise in contexts where environmental risks or burdens are unevenly distributed across populations or generations, intersecting with broader questions of vulnerability and justice that are not easily captured through traditional human-subject risk frameworks.

Taken together, this reflects a misalignment between expanding ethical expectations and the practical tools and support currently available to RECs, rather than a lack of ethical awareness. Addressing this gap does not require new ethical principles or additional approval layers, but rather proportionate, REC-facing guidance that helps integrate environmental and climate considerations into existing ethics review practices in a consistent and context-sensitive way.

The RE4GREEN Perspective: Expanding the Scope of RECs

From the RE4GREEN perspective, "expanding the scope" of RECs should not be understood as introducing new legal responsibilities, formal powers, or additional layers of ethics approval. Rather, it refers to supporting RECs to address environmental and climate considerations that are already recognised as ethically relevant

⁶ European Commission: EU Grants - How to complete your ethics self-assessment, https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/how-to-complete-your-ethics-self-assessment_en.pdf

within European and international research ethics frameworks, but that are not yet consistently operationalised in ethics review practice.

RE4GREEN emphasises that ethics review should remain proportionate, supportive, and appropriately authoritative in nature. Integrating environmental and climate considerations into REC practice is intended to encourage early ethical reflection, transparency, and responsible methodological choices, within the context of established ethics review and approval processes, without constraining scientific freedom or innovation and without increasing administrative burden for either researchers or RECs. In this sense, RECs are not expected to act as environmental regulators, but to ensure that ethically relevant environmental and climate issues are identified, assessed, and addressed where appropriate as part of their existing review and approval responsibilities.

At the same time, RE4GREEN recognises that RECs cannot be expected to address environmental and climate ethics in isolation. Effective integration depends on a broader institutional ethics ecosystem that provides access to appropriate expertise, guidance, and support, and that situates ethics review within wider research governance structures.

From the RE4GREEN perspective, supporting the integration of environmental and climate considerations into ethics review involves a limited number of practical enablers:

- Clear recognition that environmental and climate risks may be ethically relevant, allowing such considerations to be addressed, where appropriate, within the existing scope of ethics review.
- Access to guidance and training to support REC members in identifying and assessing environmental and climate-related ethical considerations alongside risks to human participants, animals, and society. At present, such materials are limited and further resources are needed. REC members are encouraged to consult the list of resources provided at the end of this guidance document, as well as the RE4GREEN training micromodules available via the [Embassy of Good Science](#).
- Integration of environmental and climate prompts into existing review tools, such as templates, checklists, or guiding questions, to support consistency and transparency without adding procedural burden. At present, such tools are limited and further development is needed. Readers are encouraged to consult the REC Environmental & Climate Ethics Reflection Tool presented in the next section as an illustrative example.

Taken together, this approach aims to strengthen the capacity of ethics review to respond to environmental and climate-related ethical challenges, while remaining fully aligned with existing research ethics governance and appraisal frameworks.

Proposed REC Environmental & Climate Ethics Review Reflection Tool

This section presents a proposed reflection tool to support RECs in identifying and considering environmental and climate-related ethical issues during ethics review. The tool is voluntary and illustrative and is intended to complement the European Commission's Guidance Note on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm in EU-funded research by translating its principles and questions into a REC-focused format that can be used within existing ethics review and approval processes. While the Commission Guidance Note primarily addresses applicants, researchers, and evaluators, the reflection tool is designed to support RECs in structured ethical reflection, without introducing new procedural requirements or additional layers of review.

1. Relevance screening (threshold question)

REC members should ask:

- a. Does the proposed research have **actual or foreseeable environmental or climate impacts**, either:
 - i. directly (e.g. emissions, resource use, pollution, biodiversity impacts), or
 - ii. indirectly (e.g. policy influence, technological deployment)?
- b. If yes → environmental and climate ethics review should be part of the ethics appraisal.

2. Research topic and purpose

REC members should ask:

- a. Does the **research topic** itself raise risks of environmental harm or ecological injustice?
**Note: For example, the Guidance Note highlights that research related to rare earths may raise environmental concerns.*
- b. Could the research contribute to:
 - i. increased greenhouse gas emissions,
 - ii. biodiversity loss,
 - iii. pollution,
 - iv. depletion of natural resources,
 - v. unequal environmental burdens across communities or generations?
- c. Are potential environmental harms **proportionate** to the expected scientific and societal benefits of the research?

3. Research methods

REC members should assess whether:

- a. The **methods chosen** are unnecessarily resource-intensive.
- b. Lower-impact alternatives (e.g. simulations, reuse of data) were considered and, if rejected, whether the justification is ethically adequate.
- c. Projects using resource-intensive methods (such as AI) describe their computing and energy needs and any measures to limit them.

4. Research practices and operations

REC members should consider whether:

- a. The project is expected to have a significant carbon footprint
- b. (Where relevant) laboratory or operational practices take into account:
 - i. use of disposable materials,
 - ii. hazardous waste,
 - iii. energy and water use.
- c. Whether sustainability measures (reduce, reuse, recycle) are embedded in the project organisation.

5. Risk–benefit and "Do No Significant Harm" (DNSH)

REC members should ask:

- a. Has the applicant identified **environmental risks** and proposed mitigation measures?
- b. Are these measures **credible, proportionate, and monitorable**?
- c. Does the project plausibly comply with the **DNSH** principle?

- d. If environmental harm is unavoidable:
 - i. is it ethically justified?
 - ii. is it minimised?
 - iii. is it transparently acknowledged?

6. Justice, inclusion, and intergenerational considerations

REC members should ask:

- a. Are environmental risks or burdens unevenly distributed (e.g. disproportionately affecting vulnerable communities)?
- b. Were affected communities or stakeholders meaningfully considered, where relevant?

7. Oversight, monitoring, and conditions

REC decisions may include:

- a. requesting additional environmental risk documentation,
- b. requiring mitigation or monitoring plans,
- c. recommending the involvement of environmental experts, whose primary responsibility is to consider the environmental impacts of the research,
- d. imposing ethics requirements related to sustainability during project implementation.

The proposed tool should be understood as an illustrative example of the types of questions that may support ethical reflection. Importantly, a range of relevant guidance documents, self-assessment tools, and review checklists addressing environmental and sustainability aspects of research ethics already exist at European, national, and institutional levels. These resources provide a strong foundation that RECs can draw on, adapt, and combine to suit disciplinary, institutional, and national contexts. Readers are encouraged to consult the resources listed below for further guidance.

List of resources:

Resource	Type of resource	Origin / issuing body	Primary target audience	Scope, focus & relevance
Ethics Review Checklist for Use of Gene Drive	Ethics review checklist	iRECS (Horizon Europe project, Grant agreement ID: 101058587)	RECs, ethics reviewers	Provides a structured, REC-facing checklist addressing ecological risks, long-term ecosystem impacts, uncertainty, reversibility, and governance of environmental harm. Offers one of the clearest operationalisations of environmental ethics within formal ethics review processes.
TechEthos D5.4 – Criteria for	Analytical report with	TechEthos (Horizon 2020 project, Grant	RECs, policymakers,	Analyses structural and substantive challenges faced by RECs when reviewing emerging technologies,

Ethical Review by RECs in Emerging Technology Research	recomm- endations	agreement ID: 101006249)	ethics organisations	including climate engineering. Highlights difficulties in assessing long-term societal and environmental harms and calls for REC-specific guidance and capacity-building.
Checklist – JRF Ethics Committee	Ethics self- assessment checklist	Johannes-Rau- Forschungsge- meinschaft (JRF) – Ethics Committee (Germany)	Researchers (indirectly RECs)	Prompts researcher reflection on ethical, societal, and environmental aspects of research, including sustainability considerations.
How to Complete Your Ethics Self-Assessment (Part 7: Environment & Safety)	Guidance document / ethics self- assessment tool	European Commission (Horizon Europe)	Horizon Europe applicants; researchers; ethics reviewers;	Mandatory ethics self-assessment guidance for Horizon Europe applicants. Part 7 operationalises environmental and safety considerations.
Environmental Sustainability as an Ethical Issue in Intensive Care Research	Peer- reviewed academic article	Springer (medical ethics & clinical research literature)	Clinicians, researchers, ethics scholars	Frames environmental sustainability and climate impacts as ethical issues in medical research, strengthening the normative basis for integrating environmental considerations into ethics discourse, but does not provide governance mechanisms or REC review tools.
DFG Sustainability Guide for Research Processes	Guidance / best- practice document	Deutsche Forschungsge- meinschaft (DFG)	Researchers, research institutions, funders	Provides practical recommendations to reduce environmental footprints across the research lifecycle (e.g. energy use, mobility, procurement). Strong on sustainability practice, but largely disconnected from ethics review procedures or explicit REC mandates.

Engaging with Citizen Scientists: Integrating Environmental and Climate Considerations into Research Practice

Executive summary

These guidelines support researchers and project teams who engage with citizen scientists across diverse fields of research and innovation. They apply to both in-person and digital citizen science, including app-based data submission and sensor-enabled participation. They highlight how environmental and climate considerations arise in citizen science activities and how these should be addressed in ways that uphold fairness, sustainability, and the commitment to “leave no one behind” in the green and digital transitions.

The guidelines invite you to uphold the ALLEA European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (reliability, honesty, respect, accountability), align with ECSA’s Ten Principles and Characteristics of Citizen Science, integrate Do No Significant Harm (DNSH)⁷ and broader environmental, climate and distributive justice considerations across the research life cycle (including indirect and transboundary impacts), and address specific challenges of citizen science such as consent, data protection, power imbalances and recognition in the context of the European Green Deal and evolving EU environmental law.

The document is structured around five stages: (1) design and planning; (2) ethics review, governance and data management; (3) working with citizen scientists in practice; (4) evaluation, learning and long-term stewardship; and (5) practical checklists and reflective questions. For rapid use, readers can start with the Checklist for researchers and the Questions to ask yourself, and then consult the relevant sections as needed. The guidelines may be adapted for ethics applications, internal standard operating procedures, and project handbooks. Researchers can use and adapt the guidelines below for ethics applications, internal standard operating procedures, and project handbooks.

Guidelines

Design and planning

This subsection outlines key environmental and climate considerations that should be taken into account when designing and planning citizen science activities.

1. Clarify purpose, roles and expectations

Define your project’s scientific and societal objectives, including any environmental or climate implications and explain why citizen science is appropriate (for example extended spatial or temporal coverage, access to local knowledge, or empowerment of affected communities). Clearly specify the roles and status of citizen scientists, including whether they act primarily as data contributors, co-researchers, co-authors, or participants in decision-making or governance processes.

⁷ The DNSH principle originates from EU sustainability policy and is used here as a high-level ethical lens to help researchers reflect on whether research activities could cause significant environmental or social harm. This guide does not provide legal guidance on DNSH compliance under the EU Taxonomy or related instruments, nor does it place such responsibilities on citizen scientists. Researchers remain responsible for addressing any formal DNSH or regulatory requirements applicable to their projects.

Describe what citizen scientists will do in practice, what skills or training are required, and what level of effort and responsibility is expected. Prepare clear, non-technical descriptions of roles, rights, and responsibilities that can be reused in information sheets, consent materials, and terms and conditions.

2. Embed DNSH and environmental ethics from the outset

Conduct a DNSH-oriented scoping of risks, including possible ecological disturbance, social and distributive impacts (who benefits, who may be harmed), and risks associated with the collection and use of data. These may include misuse or secondary use of data, for example where environmental or spatial data contribute to surveillance, inform investment or planning decisions that accelerate green gentrification, or enable exploitation of natural resources. Adjust protocols to minimise harm and document mitigation measures.

For projects in health and life sciences or areas involving biosecurity, ensure that applicable regulatory requirements are met and approved by local biosecurity committees before involving citizen scientists, and make clear which activities must be carried out or supervised by qualified professionals.

3. Plan for inclusion and fairness

Identify the groups most affected by environmental or climate implications arising from project activities and plan for their proactive inclusion, including vulnerable communities, youth, local experts and underrepresented groups that are historically or structurally under-represented in research participation, knowledge production, or decision-making processes relevant to the project domain. Offer diverse participation modes (digital and non-digital, synchronous and asynchronous) and budget for accessibility needs such as language support, interpretation, childcare or travel. Aim to design participation protocols and digital tools (such as apps and platforms) in ways that are accessible, usable, and inclusive across different levels of digital literacy, abilities, and technological access. Anticipate power imbalances and consider structures, such as advisory boards or steering groups, in which citizen scientists participating in the research can influence design, governance, and communication.

4. Fieldwork in natural landscapes

For field-based projects in natural landscapes, conduct a basic ecological and health-and-safety risk assessment in collaboration with local communities, land managers or park authorities. Agree on a simple code of conduct for fieldwork and communicate it clearly to all citizen scientists and participants before activities begin.

Ethics review, governance and data management

This subsection highlights environmental and climate considerations relevant to ethics review, research governance, and data management in citizen science activities.

1. Ethics review

Where required by national legislation, institutional policy, or disciplinary standards, citizen science projects or project proposals should be submitted to appropriate ethics review or oversight bodies, particularly when personal data, images, sensitive geodata, or information about individuals or communities are collected, or when participants may also be research subjects (for example, in surveys or interviews). Project teams should clearly explain the roles of citizen scientists (e.g. co-researchers, contributors), consent and withdrawal

mechanisms (including for long-term platforms), and how vulnerable or marginalised groups, especially those disproportionately affected by environmental or climate impacts, will be protected.

In contexts where formal ethics committees do not routinely review citizen science or non-biomedical research, researchers should seek alternative forms of ethical oversight and guidance, such as consultation with institutional ethics officers, data protection officers (DPOs), or equivalent advisory bodies. Such oversight should consider not only data protection and privacy obligations, but also environmental and climate ethics implications, including risks associated with sensitive ecological data, geolocation information, or community-level environmental knowledge.

Project teams should ensure that submissions are supported by a FAIR⁸-aligned Data Management Plan (DMP) that is supplemented by explicit measures to identify and mitigate ethical risks, including risks associated with personal, environmental, or geospatial data (such as privacy concerns, sensitive ecological information, or harmful secondary uses).

2. Data management, terms and conditions, and open science

Prepare a Data Management Plan (DMP) that covers data types, quality control, storage, access rights, retention periods, and conditions for open or controlled access. Where relevant, address environmental and climate implications of data use, such as risks linked to sensitive ecological data, locations of endangered species, or information that could unintentionally increase environmental pressures.

Apply privacy-by-design principles in apps and platforms by working with anonymous data whenever possible, and, where this is not feasible, with pseudonymised data. Limit the collection of personal data to what is strictly necessary, clarify permissions, and make privacy settings simple and accessible. Where pseudonymisation is used, keep re-identification keys separate and securely managed. For sensitive environmental or social data (such as locations of endangered species or informal settlements), consider additional protective measures, including spatial generalisation, restricted-access repositories, or delayed public release, to prevent unintended environmental or social harm.

Ensure that consent, privacy controls and terms of use are visible and understandable, shared with participants before they contribute, and consistent with the DMP and ethics approvals. When designing or using digital tools and platforms (for example, apps, sensors, online portals, AI-supported analysis), allow participants to view their data, change privacy settings and request data deletion. Allow participants to also assess and flag accessibility, potential biases and risks of reinforcing digital divides, and offer alternatives or support where possible.

3. Data ownership, traditional knowledge and benefit-sharing

Before data collection, clarify who will be considered the owner or custodian of different types of data (individual observations, community-level data, aggregated datasets, models, code) and project outputs, and how this will be reflected in licences, access conditions and acknowledgements.

When working with local, Indigenous or traditional knowledge, recognise that this may be held collectively and governed by community norms. Some knowledge should not be made openly available, especially if disclosure could lead to environmental harm, resource extraction, over-exploitation, biopiracy or cultural

⁸ Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

harm. Discuss and document benefit-sharing arrangements with relevant communities and partners, such as access to data and tools, capacity-building, co-authorship or co-branding, or (where appropriate) participation in financial benefits from commercial uses of results.

Information sheets, consent materials and terms and conditions should explain what claims researchers, institutions and third parties may make over data and knowledge, what claims citizen scientists and communities may retain, and how disputes will be handled (especially when data relate to land, natural resources or environmental stewardship).

Working with citizen scientists in practice

This subsection addresses environmental and climate considerations that may arise during the practical implementation of citizen science activities.

1. Informed consent and information

Provide layered information (a short overview plus a more detailed description) in plain language. Explain the project's purpose, methods, environmental risks and benefits, and how data and metadata will flow and be shared (including open-science aspects and whether data relate to local ecosystems, climate vulnerabilities, or sensitive ecological locations). Where relevant, explicitly address the collection and use of visual data (such as photographs, videos, images, maps, or other visual records).

Clarify how individual participants can withdraw and what happens to existing data, including whether data may be reused in future research, shared with third parties, or combined with other datasets, and under what conditions.

Where research activities affect communities, territories, or shared environmental resources, consider whether additional forms of community-level information, consultation, or consent are appropriate. In some contexts, this may include engagement with community representatives, leaders, or governance bodies before individual participation begins, particularly where research relates to land, natural resources, environmental monitoring, or collective climate vulnerabilities.

2. Avoid undue inducement and ensure voluntary participation

Offer recognition and modest incentives where appropriate (such as reimbursement of expenses, certificates or training) but avoid financial or material benefits that may pressure individuals or communities to participate especially in contexts where environmental or climate vulnerabilities may heighten dependence on such incentives. Make it clear, in writing and verbally, that participation is voluntary and that declining or withdrawing will not affect access to services, support or future collaboration.

3. Training, support and safety⁹

⁹ Citizen science raises specific ethical responsibilities with regard to research quality. Researchers should not assume that citizen scientists have prior methodological expertise. Adequate training, clear protocols, and ongoing support are essential to ensure data quality while respecting participants as collaborators rather than shifting responsibility or blame for methodological shortcomings onto them.

Provide initial and, where needed, ongoing training for citizen scientists covering data collection protocols and quality standards, use of equipment and digital tools, and safety procedures and environmental rules (e.g. how to minimise ecological impact). Training should also address research integrity and ethics, including responsible conduct, respectful engagement with communities and environments, and personal data management where applicable. Establish clear channels for support and conduct a basic risk assessment for fieldwork that addresses health (including psychological support), safety (including using equipment) and potential environmental impacts for both researchers and citizen scientists.

4. Recognition, feedback and decision-making involvement

Develop a transparent recognition plan that includes acknowledgement of data contributions, appropriate attribution of individual or collective inputs, and clear criteria for co-authorship, where relevant. Recognition may take different forms depending on the level and nature of contribution (e.g. acknowledgements, contributor lists, dataset citations, co-authorship, or public recognition), and should be communicated clearly from the outset.

Provide regular feedback through dashboards, maps, short updates, or co-interpretation sessions, highlighting where environmental or climate-related findings may have implications for local communities or ecosystems.

Where suitable, involve citizen scientists in decisions about project design and priorities, data governance and access rules, and communication formats, especially when data relate to land, resources, environmental monitoring, or climate vulnerabilities. This helps reduce power imbalances, strengthen trust, and avoid instrumentalising participants solely as data collectors.

5. Conflicts of interest and transparency

Identify and manage conflicts of interest for both professional researchers and citizen scientists, including financial and non-financial interests. Ask team members and citizen scientists in governance or decision-making roles to disclose relevant interests at project start and when circumstances change.

Particular attention should be paid to non-financial conflicts of interest, which may be less visible but can significantly influence research processes and outcomes. These may include strong personal, political, community, advocacy, or professional commitments related to the research topic, local environmental disputes, land or resource use, or anticipated policy outcomes. Project teams should raise awareness of such conflicts, facilitate reflection among participants, and provide clear guidance and examples to help identify them.

Decide how to handle disclosed conflicts in a proportionate manner, for example, by documenting them transparently, using balanced or diverse panels, clarifying roles, or avoiding situations where individuals with strong stakes are solely responsible for critical measurements, interpretation, or communication. Be transparent with participants and stakeholders about funding sources, institutional partnerships, and policy links, especially where these may raise questions about conflicts of interest, independence, advocacy, or industry influence.

Evaluation, learning and long-term stewardship

This subsection highlights environmental and climate considerations relevant to the evaluation of activities, learning processes, and the long-term responsibilities associated with citizen science research.

1. Evaluation

Plan evaluation that covers scientific quality, participant experience (e.g. motivation, perceived respect, learning), ethical performance, and the environmental and social impacts of project activities. Where appropriate, use measurable and transparent indicators to support evaluation, for example indicators related to data quality and reuse, inclusiveness and fairness of participation, handling of ethical incidents or DNSH concerns, and observed environmental or climate-related outcomes of the project.

2. Oversight and long-term stewardship

Document lessons learned and integrate them into institutional policies for citizen science, future project design, and training or micro-modules on research ethics and integrity.

For citizen science projects with long-term monitoring objectives, identify appropriate oversight institutions (e.g., public agencies, trusted repositories, community organisations or RPOs) that can advocate for the interests of all stakeholders. Develop a realistic transition plan for long-term data and platform stewardship, including open data preservation where compatible with privacy and safety, governance arrangements for ongoing access and use, and responsibilities and resources after project funding ends.

Checklist for researchers

Planning

- DNSH and environmental/social risks have been considered and mitigated.
- Potential environmental or climate implications of activities or data uses have been assessed and mitigated.
- Members of the research team as well as citizens (especially those new to citizen science) have received or will receive training on research ethics and integrity related to citizen science practice, and relevant climate/environmental and DNSH considerations.
- Risks of shifting environmental burdens or social risks to other regions (including outside the EU) have been considered (e.g., for field-based or supply-chain-related projects). These have been communicated to citizen scientists and addressed (with the research team and partners) in the impact assessment.
- Clear objectives and a documented rationale for using citizen science are defined and communicated in a form accessible to participants.
- Roles and tasks of citizen scientists are specified.
- For field-based projects (i.e., in natural landscapes), we have conducted an ecological and health-and-safety risk assessment in collaboration with land managers or park authorities, and we have clearly communicated the agreed code of conduct to all citizen scientists.
- Where relevant, health/life science and biosecurity requirements are addressed.
- Inclusion and accessibility needs are identified and resourced.
- Ethics review has been sought where required.
- A Data Management Plan (DMP) exists and covers citizen science data.
- Participants will receive clear terms and conditions consistent with the DMP.

- A risk-tier has been assigned and documented.
- A complaint mechanism exists.

Implementation

- Plain-language information and consent materials are ready.
- Training materials and sessions for citizen scientists are in place.
- Support and communication channels are established.
- Recognition, feedback, and participation-in-decision-making strategies are agreed upon within the team.
- Privacy-by-design measures are implemented in apps/platforms.
- Digital tools and platforms (e.g. apps, sensors, online portals, AI-supported analysis) are assessed not only for privacy/security but also for accessibility, potential biases, and risk of reinforcing digital divides; alternatives or support are offered where needed/possible.
- Safety and environmental rules are communicated and monitored.

Monitoring and evaluation

- Evaluation covers scientific, ethical, environmental and social dimensions.
- Red flags are actively monitored and addressed (e.g., citizen or community concerns that the research project might worsen climate vulnerabilities are not taken seriously or investigated transparently).
- Findings and data are shared in line with consent, terms & conditions, and the DMP.
- Citizen scientists receive accessible feedback on results and impacts.
- Where feasible, results are published in reputable open-access journals or repositories, avoiding predatory outlets that lack transparent peer review and clear editorial standards.
- Lessons learned feed into institutional and project-level improvements.
- Oversight institutions and long-term stewardship plans are identified for ongoing initiatives.

Questions to ask yourself (for researchers)

- Would I still consider this project ethical and fair if I were a citizen scientist participant rather than a professional researcher?
- Are citizen scientists adequately recognised, credited, and acknowledged in ways that reflect the nature and level of their contributions?
- Are citizen scientists genuinely able to opt out without losing essential benefits, access or trust?
- Have we done enough to minimise environmental and social harms associated with our activities and data uses?
- Are those most affected by climate and environmental issues meaningfully included and heard in this project?
- Does our design reflect the core principles of research integrity (reliability, honesty, respect, accountability) in a citizen science context?
- Have we done enough to maximise accessibility and minimise privacy risks associated with our activities, tools, and data practices?
- Have we identified appropriate ethics review, oversight institutions and long-term data preservation arrangements for this project?

- Are we confident that our citizen science project contributes to a just green and digital transition, that is, it prevents significant environmental harms and inequalities rather than simply relocating them in time, space, or to less visible communities?

Taking Part in Research: A Guide for Citizen Scientists on Environmental and Climate Considerations

Executive summary

This guide is for citizen scientists taking part in research that may have environmental or climate implications, including projects linked to the European Green Deal¹⁰. This means being actively involved in activities such as collecting data, interpreting results, or contributing to project decisions. This guide is designed to help you participate responsibly, understand how your contributions support environmental and climate knowledge and the Do No Significant Harm (DNSH)¹¹ principle, and avoid actions that could unintentionally cause environmental or social harm.

At a glance, this guide helps you understand:

- Your rights as a citizen scientist, including receiving clear information, choosing whether to take part, and stopping your participation at any time
- Your responsibilities, such as following project instructions, acting honestly and carefully when collecting or sharing data, and respecting the environment and others involved
- How your participation can support research that is respectful to the environment and climate and contributes to positive outcomes for communities and ecosystems

For quick use, readers may start with the Checklist for Citizen Scientists and the Questions to Ask Yourself, which provide a simple way to reflect on participation and identify potential concerns, and then consult the relevant sections as needed.

Your contribution to research is valuable and should always take place in ways that are safe, transparent, respectful, and ethically sound. In some projects, especially in health and life sciences or where biosecurity considerations are relevant, additional safeguards and requirements may apply. The project team should explain these clearly before you decide whether to participate, and you should feel free to ask questions or seek clarification if anything is unclear.

¹⁰ The European Green Deal is the European Union's comprehensive growth strategy launched in 2019, aiming to transform the EU into a modern, resource-efficient, and competitive economy. Its central goal is to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050, with an interim target to reduce net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030. The framework covers energy, industry, agriculture, transport, and biodiversity to create a sustainable, inclusive, and clean, green transition.

¹¹ "Do No Significant Harm" (DNSH) is a European Commission principle ensuring investments, particularly under the Recovery and Resilience Facility, do not cause significant environmental damage. It requires projects to meet criteria across six objectives, including climate change mitigation, adaptation, water protection, circular economy, pollution control, and biodiversity.

Before you join: understand the project

1. Project purpose and who is behind it

You should receive a clear, short description of the project's aims (for example, monitoring local heat islands or tracking biodiversity change), who coordinates the project (institutions), who funds it, and how the results are expected to be used (e.g. informing local policies, contributing to scientific publications, supporting environmental management). This information should be provided in accessible, non-technical language. Where relevant, the project should also explain whether its activities or results could create environmental or social impacts beyond the immediate study context, including effects on other communities or future generations, and what measures are taken to minimise such risks.

2. Your role as a citizen scientist

The project should explain clearly what you will do, such as making observations, uploading photos or sensor data, joining workshops, or helping interpret results, including activities that may involve natural areas or environmental data.

You are free to decide what level of involvement is realistic for you, and you are not obliged to take on tasks beyond what you agreed at the start. You can also adjust your level of involvement over time or decide to stop at any time.

3. What happens with the data you contribute

The project should explain which types of data will be collected including, where relevant, data that may be collected about you and data that you will collect or generate through your participation (for example dates, locations, measurements, photos, and any environmental or climate-related information you might gather). You should be informed on how to ask questions and feel comfortable asking them if anything is unclear. You should know where and for how long the data you will provide will be stored, how it will be protected and whether it will be openly available or shared under conditions. You should also know how you will receive feedback on results (e.g. maps, dashboards, newsletters or meetings). You should feel comfortable asking questions if anything is unclear.

4. Terms, conditions and duration

You should receive clear terms and conditions that explain how you can participate, how the data you contribute can be used, shared or reused, under which licence, and how long the project and its data infrastructure are expected to run. You should have an opportunity to read these and ask questions before you decide whether they are acceptable to you.

Your rights as a citizen scientist

1. Voluntary participation and right to withdraw

Participation is entirely voluntary. You may decline to participate or withdraw at any time, without penalty. The project should tell you how to withdraw and what will happen to the data you have already contributed including community, environmental or climate-related data.

2. Informed consent

Before you start, you should receive a clear explanation of the project and your role, information on possible environmental benefits and risks, and a consent form (paper or digital) in understandable language.

You should confirm consent only if you feel you understand what is involved. In some projects, especially in health and life sciences, additional institutional or regulatory approvals and safety rules may apply. These should also be explained.

3. Privacy and confidentiality

Privacy and confidentiality are especially important when research involves data that may indirectly reveal information about you, such as location data, observations linked to specific places, or contributions associated with identifiable individuals. This may be particularly relevant when datasets include sensitive environmental information (for example, endangered species locations, community sites, or places associated with participants).

4. Recognition and feedback

Your contribution should be acknowledged appropriately (for example in project reports, websites, or publications). You should be able to choose whether to be named or remain anonymous. The project should share results in accessible formats, such as summaries, visuals or public events, and explain how you and other participants contributed to the research (e.g., how your contributions helped advance environmental or climate understanding).

5. Involvement in decisions

Where suitable, you may be invited to help shape decisions about how data are collected and interpreted, how results are communicated, or how data are shared or reused. You are free to accept or decline these roles. Saying no should not affect your participation in the project.

6. Your knowledge, community data and benefit-sharing

If you provide local, environmental, cultural or traditional ecological knowledge to the project team, you have the right to ask how this knowledge will be used, stored and shared, whether your community or group will be recognised as a custodian of this knowledge, and what benefits are planned for you and your community if the research leads to applications or products.

You can decline to share knowledge that you or your community consider sensitive, sacred or vulnerable to misuse. Where knowledge is shared collectively, it may be important that consent and benefit-sharing are discussed at the community level, not only individually.

Your responsibilities as a citizen scientist

1. Act with honesty and care in data collection

Follow the project's instructions and protocols as closely as possible. You should not invent, alter, or selectively report observations. Inform the project team if you are unsure or may have made a mistake. These practices are an essential part of research integrity, which means producing trustworthy knowledge through honest and careful work.

Key integrity issues to keep in mind include fabrication (making up data), falsification (changing or omitting data to influence results), and selective reporting (only sharing results that support a preferred outcome). Noting uncertainties, limitations, or unexpected results is part of good research practice, especially when environmental or climate-related data may inform local decisions or policies.

You should also be aware that strong personal, professional, or community interests related to the research topic can unintentionally influence how data are collected or interpreted. Being open about such interests and following agreed protocols helps ensure that the research remains fair, credible, and useful to others.

2. Respect people's privacy

You should avoid capturing identifiable images or information about people (for example faces, license plates, house numbers) and avoid sharing other participants' personal information without consent. You should take care when posting project-related screenshots or maps on social media especially if they show sensitive environmental or location data.

3. Respect nature and local rules (Do No Significant Harm)

You should follow rules for protected areas and natural sites, including "leave no trace"¹² principles, staying on marked paths where advised, avoiding disturbing wildlife (especially during breeding seasons), and following any biosecurity instructions such as cleaning boots to avoid spreading invasive species. You should also ensure your activities do not inadvertently block access to public spaces for others or create local nuisances (noise/light) while monitoring.

Non-personal environmental data (for example animal behaviour, species presence, weather, water levels) should be gathered in the least intrusive way possible, avoiding disturbance, stress, injury or damage to animals and habitats. EU and national rules on the ethical treatment of animals also apply when research is carried out by citizen scientists. If a protocol ever feels harmful or inappropriate for animals, you should stop and contact the project team for clarification.

You should not collect samples (such as plants, animals, soil) without explicit instructions, and you should always respect local regulations and conservation rules. Take litter away and minimise your environmental footprint during field activities (e.g. choosing a sustainable mode of transport to reach sampling sites where possible).

4. Use technology responsibly

¹² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Leave_No_Trace

You should use only the official apps or tools provided by the project, keep your accounts and devices secure (for example, by using passwords and updates), and report technical problems such as GPS errors or app bugs to the project team. This is particularly important when your device collects location or environmental data that might be sensitive.

5. Support, inclusion and respect

You should treat other participants and community members with respect, welcome newcomers and value different kinds of knowledge (local, Indigenous, expert, lay). Inclusive and respectful participation strengthens environmental and climate research and ensures diverse perspectives are represented. Report to the project team any harassment or discrimination you experience or observe.

6. Be open about your interests and roles

If you or your organisation have strong interests related to the project topic (for example employment in a company, NGO or public authority involved in the issue, or a role in a campaign or court case), you should tell the project team. This does not disqualify you from taking part; it helps avoid misunderstandings and supports fair interpretation of data especially when environmental or climate issues affect different groups differently.

Checklist for citizen scientists

Before joining

- I understand what the project is about and who is organising it.
- I know what my role will be and how often I am expected to contribute.
- I have read or received an explanation of how the data I will provide will be used, stored and shared.
- I have seen the terms and conditions and know how long the project is expected to run.
- I know how to ask questions and how to withdraw if I change my mind.
- I understand whether the project has environmental or climate implications and how my contribution supports fair and sustainable outcomes.
- I have been told how the project aims to avoid shifting environmental or social harms to other communities (including outside the EU) or future generations.
- I know I will receive a short introduction or training on collecting data, protecting privacy, and minimising environmental impacts.

While participating

- I follow the agreed protocols and ask for help when unsure.
- I respect privacy, nature and local rules.
- I record uncertainties or mistakes instead of hiding them.
- I use project tools responsibly and keep my account secure.
- If I feel unsafe or uncomfortable due to the behaviour of others, I know how to report this and trust that my concerns will be taken seriously.
- If I notice potential harm to nature or unintended impacts on certain groups, such as increased exposure to climate or environmental risks, I know how to raise this with the project team and expect them to respond promptly and transparently to my concerns.

After contributing

- I stay informed about how results and findings are communicated, including whether sensitive environmental or climate-related data are handled responsibly.
- I speak up if I see potential harm, misuse of data, or risks for communities or ecosystems.
- I make use of opportunities to learn from the results (e.g., meetings, dashboards, summaries) and understand how my contribution supports environmental or climate objectives.

Questions to ask yourself

- Do I feel free to say no or to stop participating if I want to?
- Do I trust the organisations running this project to use the data I contribute responsibly?
- Am I comfortable with how my personal data and location information are handled?
- Do I understand how my contribution can help address climate and environmental challenges?
- Is my participation respectful of nature, local communities, and my own wellbeing?
- If I am invited into decision-making (e.g. about data use or communication), do I feel that my voice is genuinely listened to?
- Does this project explain who benefits from the results and who might bear any environmental costs or risks, both locally and in other places that may be affected, including longer-term environmental or societal impacts?

If your answer to one or several of these questions is "no" or "not sure," consider discussing your concerns with the project team or seeking clarification before continuing your participation.

Conclusions and Next Steps

Task 3.2 demonstrates that environmental and climate considerations can be meaningfully integrated into research ethics and integrity practice without redefining existing governance structures or imposing new procedural burdens. By working within established frameworks and focusing on operational guidance, the task helps to make environmental and climate ethics more accessible, actionable, and relevant for everyday research practice.

The materials developed under Task 3.2 provide a flexible toolkit for different audiences, including researchers, RECs, and those involved in citizen-engaged research. Their stand-alone design supports uptake across diverse contexts, while their shared conceptual grounding ensures coherence across the set. Feedback from Social Lab participants and expert reviewers, including contributors to existing RE&RI frameworks, confirmed the relevance, clarity, and practical orientation of the outputs.

Looking ahead, the impact of Task 3.2 will be supported through further activities in WP4 and WP5. Selected elements of the guidance will be adapted into training micromodules to support capacity building, while dissemination efforts will focus on making the materials accessible and usable beyond the project's immediate audience. Together, these next steps aim to support the longer-term integration of environmental and climate considerations into responsible research governance and practice across the European Research Area.

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Annex – RE4GREEN Guidance Documents (PDF Versions)

RE4GREEN ANNEX TO THE ALLEA EUROPEAN CODE OF CONDUCT FOR RESEARCH INTEGRITY

Preamble

Research plays a crucial role in shaping the pathways through which societies confront pressing global challenges, including climate change, biodiversity loss, pollution, and other forms of environmental degradation. At the same time, research, like all human activities, can leave environmental and social footprints, both through its practices and through the applications it enables. These impacts are not inherent to research but can arise unintentionally or out of a lack of considerations for these impacts. Therefore, strengthening integrity in the context of environmental and climate concerns requires supporting practices that responsibly account for and minimise such impacts. Research that aims to serve the public good must uphold high standards of rigour, transparency, and responsibility while avoiding actions that may contribute to environmental or social harm.

The [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity \(ECoC\)](#) (ALLEA, 2023) sets out the foundational principles of **reliability**, **honesty**, **respect**, and **accountability**. These principles remain central to all research activities within the European Research Area and beyond. The ECoC recognises in its 2017 revision (ALLEA, 2017) that ecosystems, cultural heritage, and the environment are aspects that must be respected in research practice. However, as environmental and climate concerns become increasingly urgent, there is a need for additional guidance that translates these broad principles into operational responsibilities for the research community.

In parallel, the European Union has established the principle of **Do No Significant Harm (DNSH)**, within its regulatory framework under the EU Taxonomy

Regulation (EU, 2020). This ensures that publicly funded activities do not undermine key environmental objectives such as climate change mitigation and adaptation, biodiversity protection, or pollution prevention. While DNSH provides an important legal benchmark, it is narrowly defined and primarily tailored to investment and economic activities. Recognising this limitation, the European Commission will soon be issuing dedicated guidance for research, offering a broader and more flexible framework for identifying, assessing, and mitigating environmental harms throughout the research lifecycle. This guidance extends beyond DNSH by addressing a wider range of environmental ethics considerations, including research topics, methods, practices and new ethics requirements. Together, these developments emphasise the need to embed environmental and climate considerations at the heart of research integrity and practice.

This Annex is intended to complement the ECoC. It offers interpretive guidance on how the existing principles and practices of the ECoC should be understood and applied through an environmental and climate lens. These interpretations remain fully compatible with the freedom of research and do not restrict the independence with which researchers formulate questions and pursue knowledge. Following the structure of the ECoC, this Annex is organised into three sections: Principles, Good Research Practices, and Violations of Research Integrity. Each section provides insights on how environmental and climate considerations can be integrated into established research integrity standards.

Principles

The principles of the ECoC remain the foundation for responsible research. This Annex does not revise or add to these principles. Instead, it clarifies how their meaning extends to the environmental and climate dimensions of research, particularly where research activities or outcomes have the potential to affect ecosystems, natural resources, or the conditions that support human and non-human life. The aim is to support the research community in interpreting the four ECoC principles in ways that reflect contemporary environmental and climate considerations.

Reliability

"Reliability in ensuring the quality of research, reflected in the design, methodology, analysis, and use of resources."

Reliability requires rigorous, well-designed, and methodologically sound research. From an environmental and climate perspective, it includes generating accurate, valid, and reproducible assessments of potential environmental implications of the research. This involves ensuring that environmental assumptions, uncertainties, and real-world feasibility considerations are accounted for in research design and execution, so that findings remain dependable and applicable in practice.

Honesty

"Honesty in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting, and communicating research in a transparent, fair, full, and unbiased way."

Honesty requires transparency on the environmental dimensions of research, including potential benefits, harms, limitations and uncertainties. It includes avoiding misrepresentation, such as overstating environmental benefits or concealing or downplaying uncertainties and potential harms and ensuring that all claims related to environmental performance or sustainability are supported by evidence and presented without exaggeration.

Respect

"Respect for colleagues, research participants, research subjects, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage, and the environment."

Respect, as recognised in the ECoC, extends to ecosystems, cultural heritage, and the environment. Interpreted in an environmental and climate context,

respect entails recognising the interdependence of human and natural systems, and the moral significance of non-human life. It includes attentiveness to how research activities or outcomes impact those most affected by environmental degradation, including Indigenous peoples, local communities, and future generations. It also involves acknowledging and engaging with relevant knowledge systems, including local, traditional, and indigenous knowledge, where appropriate.

Accountability

"Accountability for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision, and mentoring, and for its wider societal impacts."

Accountability includes responsibility for the environmental implications of research processes and outcomes. This entails careful stewardship of resources, adherence to applicable environmental obligations, and transparency toward institutions, funders, and society about environmental considerations relevant to the research. Accountability also requires monitoring and reflecting on the broader consequences that research may have for environmental and climate objectives and establishing mitigation measures when these are assessed as being harmful.

Good Research Practices

Research Environment

- Research institutions should foster a culture that acknowledges and accounts for the environmental implications of research activities and outcomes and supports responsible resource use.
- Policies on good research practice should include clear expectations for environmentally responsible conduct, consistent with applicable environmental obligations.
- Institutions should ensure that environmental considerations are not undermined by unrealistic performance pressures or incentives.
- Where research involves environmental or climate data, institutions should provide appropriate infrastructure to support its proper documentation, stewardship, and traceability.

Training, Supervision, and Mentoring

- Training in research design and methodology should, where relevant, include awareness of the environmental or climate implications of research choices.
- Ethics and integrity training should familiarise researchers with applicable environmental obligations and emerging requirements.
- Supervisors should model environmentally responsible research behaviour and support researchers in recognising when environmental considerations require specialist input.

Research Procedures

- When developing research ideas, researchers should consider whether their work may have environmental or climate impacts and seek appropriate expertise when uncertain.
- Careful and well-considered research design should include reflection on the environmental footprint of methods—such as energy use, material consumption, travel, fieldwork, or laboratory practices—and consider lower-impact equivalents where possible.
- Transparent reporting should include, where applicable, environmental assumptions, uncertainties, or contextual factors that influence the interpretation of findings.

Safeguards

- Compliance with codes, guidelines, and regulations should include meeting relevant environmental requirements, such as those relating to pollution prevention, biodiversity protection, or responsible fieldwork.
- Research involving environmental or biological subjects should seek to avoid unnecessary disturbance to ecosystems, habitats, and natural resources by following established protocols for minimising harm.
- Assessing potential harms should include identifying foreseeable environmental risks associated with the research and taking proportionate steps to avoid, minimise, or mitigate them.
- In projects involving public or community participation, environmental practices should be safe and responsible and communicated clearly.

Data Practices and Management

- Stewardship of environmental or climate-related data should ensure clear documentation, secure storage, and preservation sufficient to support reproducibility and long-term value.
- Open access to environmental data should follow FAIR principles while respecting restrictions on sensitive ecological information or community-held knowledge.
- Researchers should respect applicable rights and expectations when using community-generated environmental data, including conditions on sharing, reuse, or disclosure.

Collaborative Working

- Collaboration agreements should clarify environmental responsibilities, including how potential environmental impacts will be assessed, communicated, and addressed.
- Where collaborations involve local communities or indigenous groups connected to the environments or resources affected by the research, expectations regarding community consent, indigenous data sovereignty, and the right to decline participation should be explicitly agreed upon.
- Partners should consider the fair distribution of environmental benefits and burdens, particularly where research outcomes may disproportionately affect vulnerable or marginalised groups.

Publication, Dissemination, and Authorship

- Claims about environmental impacts, benefits, or sustainability should be accurate, evidence-based, and presented without exaggeration or misrepresentation.
- Transparency in publication should include, where relevant, assumptions about environmental conditions or impacts underlying the research, limitations, uncertainties, or contextual factors that affect interpretation or policy relevance.
- Acknowledgements should accurately reflect contributions from environmental data sources, field sites, or community-generated knowledge in line with prior agreements.
- Corrections or retractions should be issued promptly when environmental claims or assessments are found to be inaccurate or misleading.

Reviewing and Assessment

- Reviewers should ensure that environmental or climate-related claims are supported by appropriate evidence and that uncertainties are clearly acknowledged.
- Assessment of research project submissions involving environmental dimensions should consider the robustness of environmental methodologies, data, and assumptions.
- Editors should be alert to conflicts of interest where reviewers have ties to industries or activities with significant environmental stakes that may bias their assessment (e.g. fossil fuels, industrial agriculture, resource extraction), and should have appropriate policies in place to identify, disclose, and manage such conflicts, including measures such as transparency requirements, replacing reviewers where necessary, or declining to publish work where conflicts cannot be adequately addressed.
- Confidentiality obligations should extend to sensitive environmental information, such as locations of endangered species or community-held environmental knowledge, where disclosure could cause harm.

- Selectively reporting environmental results in ways that mislead stakeholders, policymakers, or affected communities.
- Suppressing or failing to disclose environmental data, especially when such omission could hide potential risks, harms, or negative findings.
- Allowing funders or sponsors with environmental interests (e.g., industrial, political, or commercial stakeholders) to influence the independence or impartiality of the research or its reporting.
- Misusing environmental or community-generated data in ways that breach agreed conditions of use, ownership, or consent.
- Disclosing sensitive environmental information (such as the location of endangered species or fragile ecosystems) where such disclosure could cause harm.
- Accusing others of environmental misconduct or harm in a malicious or unsubstantiated way.

Serious forms of such practices may be sanctionable. All require prevention and correction through training, supervision, and a supportive research environment.

Dealing with Violations and Allegations of Misconduct

The principles for handling allegations of research misconduct apply equally to cases involving environmental or climate-relevant research. Investigations should be fair, consistent, confidential, and transparent, and should avoid conflicts of interest, including those arising from financial, organisational, or commercial interests and interests linked to environmentally relevant research outcomes. Processes should protect the rights of all parties involved, including bona fide whistle-blowers who may raise concerns about environmental risks, misrepresentation of environmental impacts, or unethical use of environmental or community data. Investigations should consider whether institutional structures, pressures, or incentives contributed to the breach, and should ensure that appropriate restorative or corrective action is taken when allegations are upheld or dismissed.

Violations of Research Integrity

Research Misconduct and other Unacceptable Practices

Fabrication, falsification, and plagiarism (FFP) are fundamental violations of research integrity. When research has environmental or climate relevance, these forms of misconduct may result in inappropriate environmental decisions or policies, or obscure potential harms. Beyond FFP, breaches of good research practice include activities that distort the research record or undermine the integrity of the research process, for example through misleading reporting, inappropriate influence, misuse of data, or harmful disclosure practices. In an environmental and climate context, these may include, but are not confined to:

- Misrepresenting or exaggerating environmental benefits, sustainability claims, or climate impacts ("greenwashing"), including withholding information regarding relevant uncertainties or limitations.

Further Reading

1. ALLEA | All European Academies. (2023). The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity – Revised Edition 2023. ALLEA. <https://doi.org/10.26356/ECOC>
2. ALLEA | All European Academies. (2017). The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity – Revised Edition 2023. ALLEA. <https://www.allea.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/ALLEA-European-Code-of-Conduct-for-Research-Integrity-2017.pdf>
3. EU | European Union (2020). Regulation (EU) 2020/852 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 June 2020 on the establishment of a framework to facilitate sustainable investment, and amending Regulation (EU) 2019/2088. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32020R0852>

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GOING BEYOND HARM: A STARTING GUIDE TO ENVIRONMENTAL & CLIMATE CONSIDERATIONS IN RESEARCH ETHICS

Executive Summary

This starting guide supports the integration of environmental and climate considerations into research ethics practice beyond harm-based assessment. It is intended for researchers, research teams, research ethics committees (RECs), evaluators, and project coordinators involved in the design, conduct, and review of research.

While existing ethics frameworks primarily focus on the identification and prevention of harm (particularly risks to human participants) research activities may raise ethically relevant environmental and climate considerations even where no significant environmental harm is expected. These considerations include questions of responsibility, precaution, justice, fairness, participation, and the longer-term implications of research assumptions, methods, and outputs. This guide complements, but does not replace, the European Commission's forthcoming Guidance Note on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm in EU-funded research. Rather than introducing prescriptive rules, it adopts a reflective and context-sensitive approach based on guiding questions and illustrative examples.

The guidance is structured around three complementary dimensions of environmentally and climate-responsible research:

- **Responsible and precautionary research:** encouraging reflection on research design, assumptions, methodological choices, and transparency
- **Just and fair research:** addressing the distribution of benefits, burdens, risks, and intergenerational implications
- **Participatory and inclusive research:** focusing on inclusion, pluralism, and recognition of diverse knowledge systems

The core message of this guide is that environmental and climate considerations are not limited to risk mitigation. Ethical reflection may also be warranted in relation to how research frames problems, shapes decision-making, and influences societal and environmental trajectories. The guide is designed for flexible use across disciplines and research contexts, supporting ethical reflection, documentation, and discussion within research teams and ethics review processes.

How to Use this Guide

1. Screen for harms first

Use the forthcoming EC Guidance Note on assessing and managing environmental harms to identify and mitigate potential harms linked to your research topic, methods, and practices. This process may be complemented by structured tools, such as the RE4GREEN Risk Assessment Tool (RE4GREEN, 2026), to support systematic reflection on environmental and climate-related risks.

2. Then go beyond harm

Use this guide to reflect on responsibility and precaution, justice and fairness, and participation and inclusion, including ethical issues that may still be relevant even when significant environmental harm is unlikely.

3. Record your choices

Document what you decided, why these decisions were taken, and how you will monitor and revise your approach over time (e.g. in ethics materials, project governance, and communication with stakeholders).

Introduction

Environmental and climate considerations are increasingly recognised as integral to responsible research practice. However, as recent research has highlighted, there is a structural gap in the current ethics landscape (Bourban, 2026) and governance (RE4GREEN, 2025). Existing Research Ethics (RE) literature and frameworks focus primarily on human participants and the ethical acceptability of research involving them, while environmental and climate ethics focus on ecological systems, justice, and sustainability. The two domains rarely intersect. As a result, researchers often lack clear ethical foundations for understanding how their work may engage environmental or climate responsibilities such as questions of responsibility, environmental and climate justice, or long-term environmental implications. The European Commission's (EC) forthcoming Guidance Note on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm in EU-funded research represents an important development bridging this gap. It offers a clear and practical framework to help applicants, researchers, and ethics evaluators identify, assess, and manage potential environmental harms within EU-funded research. This guide builds on and complements that work.

Environmental and climate considerations in RE extend beyond questions of harm. Research activities can raise ethical concerns even when no significant environmental harm is expected, such as when research assumptions, models, or design choices may influence long-term environmental or societal trajectories. This starting guide aims to embed key ethical considerations that are not always captured by harm-based assessments alone into RE practice, helping researchers and evaluators identify relevant environmental and climate considerations during project design, execution and evaluation. It does so by structuring the guidance around three complementary dimensions of environmentally and climate-responsible research.

Given the diversity of research domains, methods, and contexts, it is not possible to define a single set of actions that would be appropriate in all cases. For this reason, the guide adopts a reflective approach based on guiding questions and illustrative examples, rather than prescriptive rules. This approach is intended to support context-sensitive ethical reflection, enabling researchers and evaluators to identify relevant environmental and climate considerations in light of their specific research activities.

This guide does not replace the Commission's guidance note on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm, and it is not intended to serve as a risk-assessment tool.

Responsible and Precautionary Research

This section focuses on how research can be designed and conducted in contexts where research activities may have environmental or climate relevance, particularly where activities are complex, uncertain, or potentially far-reaching in their effects. The expectations outlined in the EC's Guidance Note on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm, such as avoiding unnecessary harm, considering less harmful alternatives, and ensuring that research topics, methods, and practices are not likely to generate significant harm are foundational to ethical research.

Extending beyond harm avoidance, this section supports reflection on how research choices, methods, and assumptions interact with broader environmental and climate dynamics. It invites the reader to consider not only whether harm is likely to occur, but also how research practices may reinforce particular pathways, norms, or dependencies in contexts characterised by complexity and uncertainty.

1. Integrate environmental and climate considerations into everyday research governance¹

Questions to consider:

- How are environmental and climate reflections included in team discussions, planning or documentation?
- How do our procurement, data management, or infrastructure decisions consider environmental or climate relevance, even when these are not the primary focus of the research?
- How is responsibility for raising and documenting environmental and climate considerations clearly understood within the research team?

¹This dimension focuses on research governance at the project and team level, including the responsibilities of individual researchers, project consortia, and relevant organisational units.

Example:

A consortium adds a short environmental reflection item to its regular meeting agenda, ensuring that environmental considerations become part of ongoing decision-making rather than a one-off consideration.

2. Reflect on the assumptions embedded in your research

Questions to consider:

- What do I assume to be necessary, normal, or unavoidable in my research?
- Do these assumptions reinforce patterns that could have environmental or climate implications?
- Could alternative approaches challenge or unsettle these assumptions?

Example:

A public health research project on heatwave prevention relies mainly on data collected through smartphone apps, thus assuming that everyone has a smartphone. Reflecting on this assumption may reveal that people with limited digital access are underrepresented in the dataset, including groups living in poorly insulated housing or in urban areas with higher heat exposure. As a result, certain forms of climate-related environmental vulnerability may be insufficiently captured in the evidence base used to understand heat risk and inform adaptation measures. This raises ethical questions about how research assumptions shape which climate impacts, environments, and populations are made visible in research and which ones remain overlooked.

3. Consider your sphere of influence, not only your direct impacts

Questions to consider:

- Could my method, dataset or workflow become a template that others follow?
- Might my work normalise certain approaches in the field?
- Could downstream use of my outputs have environmental or climate implications beyond this project that I have not yet considered?

Example:

A research project develops a model to compare cities or regions for policy or investment purposes based primarily on economic performance indicators, without integrating environmental or climate-related factors. While this may reflect methodological or data limitations, the model's influence may extend beyond the project itself if it is reused by policymakers, consultants, or other researchers. In such cases, the

model can contribute to decision-making frameworks that systematically prioritise economic metrics while downplaying climate risks such as heat exposure, environmental quality, or climate resilience. Reflecting on the project's sphere of influence highlights the ethical responsibility to consider how research outputs may shape environmentally relevant decisions and priorities beyond their original research context.

4. Practice transparency

Questions to consider:

- What trade-offs shaped my methodological choices (e.g., convenience vs. efficiency)?
- Were environmentally preferable alternatives considered?
- Can I briefly explain why certain options were selected?

Example:

A research team models future economic trends while holding environmental and climate conditions constant for the sake of analytical simplicity. While such simplifications are common in research, practising transparency involves explicitly stating this assumption and explaining its implications. In particular, users of the research should be able to understand that the projections do not account for factors such as climate impacts, environmental degradation, or resource constraints that could affect economic feasibility or long-term sustainability. Making these limitations explicit supports responsible use of the results in contexts where environmental and climate conditions are likely to influence outcomes.

Just and Fair Research

This section focuses on questions of fairness that arise from how research and innovation affect people, communities, and future generations. It addresses how benefits, burdens, risks, and opportunities associated with research are distributed, and how these effects may vary across social, geographic, and temporal contexts. The guidance uses selected justice perspectives as practical lenses to support ethical reflection.

1. Consider how benefits and burdens are distributed (distributive justice)

Questions to consider:

- What kinds of benefits, opportunities, or advantages may arise from this research (scientific, societal, economic, environmental)?
- Who is likely to benefit from the knowledge, technologies, or outcomes produced by this research?
- Who may bear costs, limitations, or unintended consequences associated with the research or its outcomes?
- Who owns, controls, and can access the data and the outputs of the research? Does the project respect community or Indigenous data governance where relevant (including conditions for sharing and reuse)? (e.g., [CARE principles for Indigenous data governance](#))

Example:

A research project uses environmental or socio-economic data collected in low- and middle-income countries. However, most of the research benefits, such as high-impact publications, follow-on funding, or agenda-setting influence, accrue to institutions based in the Global North. Reflecting on this distribution highlights potential imbalances between those who contribute data or local knowledge and those who primarily benefit from the research outputs.

2. Consider impacts across generations (intergenerational justice)

Questions to consider:

- How might this research affect future generations, even if impacts are not immediate?
- Does the research contribute to pathways that limit future options or create long-term dependencies?
- How are we weighing short-term benefits against potential long-term environmental or societal consequences?

Example:

A research project prioritises short-term efficiency gains through the rapid deployment of a technology without considering its long-term resource demands or disposal implications. Reflecting on intergenerational justice highlights whether alternative approaches could better preserve options and resources for future generations.

3. Attend to historical and structural inequalities (restorative justice)

Questions to consider:

- Does this research take place in contexts shaped by past injustices, extractive practices², or long-standing inequalities, e.g. in formerly colonised countries?
- Could the research unintentionally reproduce or reinforce these patterns?
- Are there opportunities for us to acknowledge past harms, support repair, or ensure reciprocity in research relationships?

Example:

A research project is conducted in a region that has historically been subject to extractive research practices, where data and resources were taken without clear benefits for local communities. Reflecting on restorative justice invites consideration of how the project can engage more respectfully, acknowledge this history, and explore forms of reciprocity or benefit-sharing.

Participatory and Inclusive Research

Research engages diverse social contexts, values, and forms of knowledge. Ethical reflection, therefore, extends beyond outcomes to questions of who participates in research and decision-making as well as whose knowledge is treated as legitimate. Where research has environmental or climate implications, these questions are particularly important because research may affect shared environments, local practices, and long-term societal and environmental trajectories. This section focuses on participation, pluralism, inclusion and respecting multiple epistemologies as dimensions of responsible research practice, particularly where research affects communities, relies on local knowledge, or informs societal decisions. Participation is meaningful when contributors can influence research questions, the interpretation of findings, or the use of results, rather than being limited to data provision alone.

²Extractive research practices refer to approaches in which data, knowledge, or resources are primarily collected from individuals or communities without meaningful participation, transparency, recognition, or fair sharing of benefits arising from the research.

1. Reflect on who is included in decision-making (procedural justice)

Questions to consider:

- Who is involved in defining research questions, methods, or priorities?
- Are we meaningfully consulting affected groups and individuals during the design and implementation of the research?
- Are participation processes designed so that they enable affected groups to realistically take part?

Example:

A consortium designs an environmental monitoring study without consulting local communities. Procedural justice invites reflection on whether earlier or more systematic engagement could improve both inclusiveness and research quality.

2. Recognise whose knowledge and perspectives are valued (epistemic and recognitional justice)

Questions to consider:

- Whose knowledge is treated as legitimate in this research?
- Are we prioritising certain forms of knowledge, experience, or expertise over others?
- Are we systematically undervaluing certain perspectives or experiences or treating them as less credible?
- Are the perspectives, values, or practices of affected groups acknowledged and respected?
- Are all contributions to the research process appropriately credited?

Example:

A climate adaptation project relies exclusively on technical models developed by external experts, while local or experiential knowledge is not considered relevant to the research. Reflecting on epistemic and recognition justice highlights whether important insights are being overlooked and whether some perspectives are implicitly treated as less credible or valuable.

3. Reflect on how people are involved in the conduct of research

Questions to consider:

- Are we involving participants in research activities that relate directly to environmental or climate conditions in their local context (e.g., observations, monitoring, interpretation of change)?

- Do participatory roles allow contributors to share context-specific environmental knowledge, lived experience, or observations that may not be captured through technical data alone?
- Are we informing participants about how their contributions relate to environmental or climate questions addressed by the research, including how data will be used, shared (e.g., as open data where applicable, or generalised/withheld where precise information could cause environmental harm), and interpreted?
- Are appropriate support, feedback, or training provided to enable meaningful participation in environmentally or climate-relevant research activities?

Example:

A project collects environmental observations through a citizen science platform but limits participant involvement to data submission, without explaining how observations contribute to understanding local environmental change. Reflecting on participation in practice highlights whether participants could be more meaningfully engaged through feedback, shared interpretation of results, or contextual discussion of environmental trends.

Conclusion

This starting guide provides a structured entry point for reflecting on environmental and climate considerations in research ethics beyond the identification and management of harm. By focusing on responsible and precautionary research practice, fairness of impacts across society and generations, and participation and pluralism in research and decision-making, the guide supports early-stage ethical reflection during project design and evaluation. This guide is intended to complement existing ethics procedures and the EC's guidance on environmental harm, not to replace formal risk assessment or ethical review. Its questions and examples are designed to be used flexibly, supporting discussion within research teams, RECs, and evaluation processes.

Further Reading

Applying these considerations in practice also depends on appropriate awareness and capacity among researchers, ethics reviewers, and evaluators. Environmental and climate ethics are evolving fields, and continuous learning is essential to ensure that ethical reflection keeps pace with scientific, technological, and societal developments. The process and outcomes of ethical reflection may be further strengthened where researchers and reviewers engage with relevant guidance and training materials through preparatory or practice-oriented activities. To support such capacity-building, RE4GREEN has developed a set of training materials on environmental and climate ethics, which are openly available through the [Embassy of Good Science](#).

1. RE4GREEN (2026). Recommendations on environmental and climate ethics amendment of risk assessment strategies. Deliverable D3.2, RE4GREEN project, Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement No. 101131706.
2. Bourban, M., Lenzi, D., Sørensen, M. et al. Convergences and Gaps between Environmental Ethics, Climate Ethics, and Research Ethics: A Scoping Review. *Sci Eng Ethics* (2026). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-025-00575-8>
3. RE4GREEN (2025). Gap analysis of research ethics and integrity resources for R&I in general and new climate and environmental technologies in particular. Deliverable D1.3, RE4GREEN project, Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement No. 101131706.

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TOWARD AN EXPANDED SCOPE OF RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEES: INTEGRATING ENVIRONMENTAL AND CLIMATE ETHICS

Executive Summary

This guidance supports Research Ethics Committees (RECs) in integrating environmental and climate considerations into existing ethics review practices. It is intended primarily for REC members, ethics reviewers, ethics administrators, and institutional actors involved in research governance, while also being relevant to researchers and evaluators interacting with ethics review processes.

Environmental degradation, climate change, and biodiversity loss are increasingly recognised within European and international research ethics frameworks as ethically relevant concerns. However, existing REC mandates, expertise, and review tools were largely developed in response to biomedical and human-subject research and are not always structured to systematically address environmental or climate-related ethical issues. Rather than introducing new ethical principles, responsibilities, or procedural layers, this guidance adopts a supportive and proportionate approach. From the RE4GREEN perspective, "expanding the scope" of RECs refers to strengthening the capacity of ethics review to address environmental and climate considerations that are already embedded within contemporary research ethics and governance frameworks.

To support practical implementation, the guidance provides:

- Conceptual framing of the evolving role of RECs in relation to environmental and climate ethics
- Analysis of structural gaps and challenges in current ethics review practice
- A voluntary and illustrative Environmental & Climate Ethics Review Reflection Tool
- A curated set of existing resources relevant to REC practice

This guidance is designed to complement, and operate alongside, existing ethics appraisal procedures and the forthcoming Guidance Note on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm in EU-funded research by the European Commission.

Background & Evolution of RECs

Research Ethics Committees (RECs) were originally established to protect the rights, dignity, and well-being of human participants, particularly within medical and health-related research. Their core procedures and review practices developed in response to concrete risks associated with biomedical experimentation, with a primary focus on informed consent, the proportionality of risks and benefits, and the protection of vulnerable individuals.

Over time, ethical review in research has broadened beyond individual participants to include animals, communities, and society at large, reflecting growing awareness of the social, distributive, and long-term impacts of research activities. In parallel, environmental degradation, climate change, and biodiversity loss have increasingly been recognised as factors that shape human well-being and societal resilience. Environmental and climate ethics have therefore emerged as a relevant extension of contemporary research ethics, grounded in the interdependence of human and ecological systems.

The institutionalisation of ethics review has, however, developed unevenly across disciplines and national contexts. While RECs are firmly established in biomedical research and in parts of the social sciences, this is not the case across all research domains. In many technical disciplines, engineering fields, and parts of the environmental sciences (especially where research does not involve direct interaction with human participants) formal institutional REC structures are weakly institutionalised or absent. Even where RECs exist, their review practices do not always systematically address environmental or climate considerations.

As a result, research activities with potential environmental or climate impacts often fall outside established ethics review practices despite their ethical relevance. Findings from [RE4GREEN Deliverable D1.3](#)¹ confirm that existing research ethics and integrity guidance largely treats environmental considerations peripherally, and that training resources for ethics reviewers rarely address environmental or climate ethics in a structured way.

These developments highlight a gradual expansion of ethical expectations in research, alongside persistent gaps in how environmental and climate considerations are reflected in ethics review practice. This underlines the need for clear, proportionate, and supportive guidance that helps RECs integrate such considerations into existing review processes, without altering their core role or increasing administrative burden.

Normative Shift: The Environment in European and International Research Ethics Frameworks

European and international research ethics frameworks increasingly recognise environmental protection and sustainability as integral components of responsible research conduct. This reflects a broader understanding that environmental degradation, climate change, and biodiversity loss are not external to research ethics, but are closely connected to human well-being, societal resilience, and justice.

At the European level, the [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#)² explicitly includes respect for the environment and ecosystems as part of responsible research practice across disciplines. Similarly, the revised [Declaration of Helsinki \(2024\)](#)³ introduces an explicit requirement for medical research to be designed and conducted in ways that avoid or minimise environmental harm and promote ecological sustainability. While the Declaration of Helsinki is specific to medical research, it reflects a wider normative shift that links environmental harm to ethical responsibilities such as risk–benefit assessment, responsibility, and justice.

Within the EU research governance framework, this normative shift is further operationalised through Horizon Europe ethics requirements and the application of the Do No Significant Harm (DNSH) principle. The forthcoming European Commission Guidance Note on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm in EU-funded research provides practical support for applicants, beneficiaries, and ethics evaluators in identifying, assessing, and mitigating environmental risks across the research lifecycle. By explicitly linking environmental harm to established ethical principles such as scientific quality, social value, justice, and proportionality, the Guidance Note confirms that environmental and climate considerations form part of ethical appraisal rather than a separate or optional concern.

Taken together, these developments indicate that environmental and climate ethics are already embedded within the normative foundations of European and international research ethics. The challenge for ethics review is therefore not to introduce new ethical principles, but to support the consistent and proportionate integration of these existing expectations into ethics review practice, in ways that are feasible across diverse research contexts.

¹RE4GREEN (2025). Gap analysis of research ethics and integrity resources for R&I in general and new climate and environmental technologies in particular. Deliverable D1.3, RE4GREEN project, Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement No. 101131706.

²ALLEA | All European Academies. (2023). The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity – Revised Edition 2023. ALLEA. <https://doi.org/10.26356/ECOC>

³World Medical Association. World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki: Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Participants. JAMA. 2025;333(1):71–74. doi:10.1001/jama.2024.21972

From Ethical Expectations to Ethics Review Practice: Gaps and Challenges for RECs

European research ethics policy increasingly recognises environmental and climate considerations as ethically relevant. [Horizon Europe ethics requirements](#)⁴, the application of the Do No Significant Harm (DNSH) principle, and the forthcoming European Commission Guidance Note all confirm that potential environmental harms should be identified and addressed as part of ethical appraisal. In practice, however, these expectations are not yet consistently reflected in ethics review processes.

This gap is partly rooted in the historical development of RECs. REC mandates, expertise, and review tools were largely shaped in response to biomedical research and research involving direct human participation. As a result, ethics review frameworks are generally better equipped to assess immediate and individual-level risks rather than indirect, cumulative, long-term, or environmentally mediated impacts. Environmental and climate considerations may therefore be addressed unevenly or implicitly treated as falling outside the core scope of ethics review.

These challenges are particularly visible in research involving complex infrastructures, advanced technologies, or data-intensive methods, such as the use of artificial intelligence, where environmental impacts may arise through energy use, resource consumption, or downstream effects. They also arise in contexts where environmental risks or burdens are unevenly distributed across populations or generations, intersecting with broader questions of vulnerability and justice that are not easily captured through traditional human-subject risk frameworks.

Taken together, this reflects a misalignment between expanding ethical expectations and the practical tools and support currently available to RECs, rather than a lack of ethical awareness. Addressing this gap does not require new ethical principles or additional approval layers, but rather proportionate, REC-facing guidance that helps integrate environmental and climate considerations into existing ethics review practices in a consistent and context-sensitive way.

⁴European Commission: EU Grants - How to complete your ethics self-assessment, https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/how-to-complete-your-ethics-self-assessment_en.pdf

The RE4GREEN Perspective: Expanding the Scope of RECs

From the RE4GREEN perspective, “expanding the scope” of RECs should not be understood as introducing new legal responsibilities, formal powers, or additional layers of ethics approval. Rather, it refers to supporting RECs to address environmental and climate considerations that are already recognised as ethically relevant within European and international research ethics frameworks, but that are not yet consistently operationalised in ethics review practice.

RE4GREEN emphasises that ethics review should remain proportionate, supportive, and appropriately authoritative in nature. Integrating environmental and climate considerations into REC practice is intended to encourage early ethical reflection, transparency, and responsible methodological choices, within the context of established ethics review and approval processes, without constraining scientific freedom or innovation and without increasing administrative burden for either researchers or RECs. In this sense, RECs are not expected to act as environmental regulators, but to ensure that ethically relevant environmental and climate issues are identified, assessed, and addressed where appropriate as part of their existing review and approval responsibilities.

At the same time, RE4GREEN recognises that RECs cannot be expected to address environmental and climate ethics in isolation. Effective integration depends on a broader institutional ethics ecosystem that provides access to appropriate expertise, guidance, and support, and that situates ethics review within wider research governance structures.

From the RE4GREEN perspective, supporting the integration of environmental and climate considerations into ethics review involves a limited number of practical enablers:

- Clear recognition that environmental and climate risks may be ethically relevant, allowing such considerations to be addressed, where appropriate, within the existing scope of ethics review.
- Access to guidance and training to support REC members in identifying and assessing environmental and climate-related ethical considerations alongside risks to human participants, animals, and society. At present, such materials are limited and further resources are needed. REC members are encouraged to consult the list of resources provided at the end of this guidance document, as well as the RE4GREEN training micromodules available via the [Embassy of Good Science](#).
- Integration of environmental and climate prompts into existing review tools, such as templates, checklists, or guiding questions, to support consistency and transparency without adding procedural burden. At present, such tools are limited and further development is needed. Readers are encouraged to consult the REC Environmental & Climate Ethics Reflection Tool presented in the next section as an illustrative example.

Taken together, this approach aims to strengthen the capacity of ethics review to respond to environmental and climate-related ethical challenges, while remaining fully aligned with existing research ethics governance and appraisal frameworks.

Proposed REC Environmental & Climate Ethics Review Reflection Tool

This section presents a proposed reflection tool to support RECs in identifying and considering environmental and climate-related ethical issues during ethics review. The tool is voluntary and illustrative and is intended to complement the European Commission's Guidance Note on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm in EU-funded research by translating its principles and questions into a REC-focused format that can be used within existing ethics review and approval processes. While the Commission Guidance Note primarily addresses applicants, researchers, and evaluators, the reflection tool is designed to support RECs in structured ethical reflection, without introducing new procedural requirements or additional layers of review.

1. Relevance screening (threshold question)

REC members should ask:

- Does the proposed research have actual or foreseeable environmental or climate impacts, either:
 - directly (e.g. emissions, resource use, pollution, biodiversity impacts), or
 - indirectly (e.g. policy influence, technological deployment)?
- If yes → environmental and climate ethics review should be part of the ethics appraisal.

2. Research topic and purpose

REC members should ask:

- Does the research topic itself raise risks of environmental harm or ecological injustice? **Note: For example, the Guidance Note highlights that research related to rare earths may raise environmental concerns.*
- Could the research contribute to:
 - increased greenhouse gas emissions,
 - biodiversity loss,
 - pollution,
 - depletion of natural resources,
 - unequal environmental burdens across communities or generations?
- Are potential environmental harms proportionate to the expected scientific and societal benefits of the research?

3. Research methods

REC members should assess whether:

- The methods chosen are unnecessarily resource-intensive.
- Lower-impact alternatives (e.g. simulations, reuse of data) were considered and, if rejected, whether the justification is ethically adequate.
- Projects using resource-intensive methods (such as AI) describe their computing and energy needs and any measures to limit them.

4. Research practices and operations

REC members should consider whether:

- The project is expected to have a significant carbon footprint
- (Where relevant) laboratory or operational practices take into account:
 - use of disposable materials,
 - hazardous waste,
 - energy and water use.
- Whether sustainability measures (reduce, reuse, recycle) are embedded in the project organisation.

5. Risk–benefit and “Do No Significant Harm” (DNSH)

REC members should ask:

- a. Has the applicant identified environmental risks and proposed mitigation measures?
- b. Are these measures credible, proportionate, and monitorable?
- c. Does the project plausibly comply with the DNSH principle?
- d. If environmental harm is unavoidable:
 - i. is it ethically justified?
 - ii. is it minimised?
 - iii. is it transparently acknowledged?

6. Justice, inclusion, and intergenerational considerations

REC members should consider:

- a. Are environmental risks or burdens unevenly distributed (e.g. disproportionately affecting vulnerable communities)?
- b. Were affected communities or stakeholders meaningfully considered, where relevant?

7. Oversight, monitoring, and conditions

REC decisions may include:

- a. Requesting additional environmental risk documentation,
- b. Requiring mitigation or monitoring plans,
- c. Recommending the involvement of environmental experts, whose primary responsibility is to consider the environmental impacts of the research,
- d. Imposing ethics requirements related to sustainability during project implementation.

The proposed tool should be understood as an illustrative example of the types of questions that may support ethical reflection. Importantly, a range of relevant guidance documents, self-assessment tools, and review checklists addressing environmental and sustainability aspects of research ethics already exist at European, national, and institutional levels. These resources provide a strong foundation that RECs can draw on, adapt, and combine to suit disciplinary, institutional, and national contexts. Readers are encouraged to consult the resources listed below for further guidance.

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List of resources

Resource	Type of resource	Origin/issuing body	Primary target audience	Scope, focus & relevance
Ethics Review Checklist for Use of Gene Drive	Ethics review checklist	iRECS (Horizon Europe project, Grant agreement ID: 101058587)	RECs, ethics reviewers	Provides a structured, REC-facing checklist addressing ecological risks, long-term ecosystem impacts, uncertainty, reversibility, and governance of environmental harm. Offers one of the clearest operationalisations of environmental ethics within formal ethics review processes.
TechEthos D5.4 – Criteria for Ethical Review by RECs in Emerging Technology Research	Analytical report with recommendations	TechEthos (Horizon 2020 project, Grant agreement ID: 101006249)	RECs, policymakers, ethics organisations	Analyses structural and substantive challenges faced by RECs when reviewing emerging technologies, including climate engineering. Highlights difficulties in assessing long-term societal and environmental harms and calls for REC-specific guidance and capacity-building.
Checklist – JRF Ethics Committee	Ethics self-assessment checklist	Johannes-Rau-Forschungsgemeinschaft (JRF) – Ethics Committee (Germany)	Researchers (indirectly RECs)	Prompts researcher reflection on ethical, societal, and environmental aspects of research, including sustainability considerations.
How to Complete Your Ethics Self-Assessment (Part 7: Environment & Safety)	Guidance document / ethics self-assessment tool	European Commission (Horizon Europe)	Horizon Europe applicants; researchers; ethics reviewers;	Mandatory ethics self-assessment guidance for Horizon Europe applicants. Part 7 operationalises environmental and safety considerations.
Environmental Sustainability as an Ethical Issue in Intensive Care Research	Peer-reviewed academic article	Springer (medical ethics & clinical research literature)	Clinicians, researchers, ethics scholars	Frames environmental sustainability and climate impacts as ethical issues in medical research, strengthening the normative basis for integrating environmental considerations into ethics discourse, but does not provide governance mechanisms or REC review tools.
DFG Sustainability Guide for Research Processes	Guidance / best-practice document	Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG)	Researchers, research institutions, funders	Provides practical recommendations to reduce environmental footprints across the research lifecycle (e.g. energy use, mobility, procurement). Strong on sustainability practice, but largely disconnected from ethics review procedures or explicit REC mandates.

ENGAGING WITH CITIZEN SCIENTISTS: INTEGRATING ENVIRONMENTAL AND CLIMATE CONSIDERATIONS INTO RESEARCH PRACTICE

Executive Summary

These guidelines support researchers and project teams who engage with citizen scientists across diverse fields of research and innovation. They apply to both in-person and digital citizen science, including app-based data submission and sensor-enabled participation. They highlight how environmental and climate considerations arise in citizen science activities and how these should be addressed in ways that uphold fairness, sustainability, and the commitment to “leave no one behind” in the green and digital transitions.

The guidelines invite you to uphold the ALLEA European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (reliability, honesty, respect, accountability), align with ECSA's Ten Principles and Characteristics of Citizen Science, integrate Do No Significant Harm (DNSH)¹ and broader environmental, climate and distributive justice considerations across the research life cycle (including indirect and transboundary impacts), and address specific challenges of citizen science such as consent, data protection, power imbalances and recognition in the context of the European Green Deal and evolving EU environmental law.

The document is structured around five stages: (1) design and planning; (2) ethics review, governance and data management; (3) working with citizen scientists in practice; (4) evaluation, learning and long-term stewardship; and (5) practical checklists and reflective questions. For rapid use, readers can start with the Checklist for researchers and the Questions to ask yourself, and then consult the relevant sections as needed. The guidelines may be adapted for ethics applications, internal standard operating procedures, and project handbooks. Researchers can use and adapt the guidelines below for ethics applications, internal standard operating procedures, and project handbooks.

Guidelines

Design and planning

This subsection outlines key environmental and climate considerations that should be taken into account when designing and planning citizen science activities.

1. Clarify purpose, roles and expectations

Define your project's scientific and societal objectives, including any environmental or climate implications and explain why citizen science is appropriate (for example extended spatial or temporal coverage, access to local knowledge, or empowerment of affected communities). Clearly specify the roles and status of citizen scientists, including whether they act primarily as data contributors, co-researchers, co-authors, or participants in decision-making or governance processes.

Describe what citizen scientists will do in practice, what skills or training are required, and what level of effort and responsibility is expected. Prepare clear, non-technical descriptions of roles, rights, and responsibilities that can be reused in information sheets, consent materials, and terms and conditions.

2. Embed DNSH and environmental ethics from the outset

Conduct a DNSH-oriented scoping of risks, including possible ecological disturbance, social and distributive impacts (who benefits, who may be harmed), and risks associated with the collection and use of data.

¹The DNSH principle originates from EU sustainability policy and is used here as a high-level ethical lens to help researchers reflect on whether research activities could cause significant environmental or social harm. This guide does not provide legal guidance on DNSH compliance under the EU Taxonomy or related instruments, nor does it place such responsibilities on citizen scientists. Researchers remain responsible for addressing any formal DNSH or regulatory requirements applicable to their projects.

These may include misuse or secondary use of data, for example where environmental or spatial data contribute to surveillance, inform investment or planning decisions that accelerate green gentrification, or enable exploitation of natural resources. Adjust protocols to minimise harm and document mitigation measures.

For projects in health and life sciences or areas involving biosecurity, ensure that applicable regulatory requirements are met and approved by local biosecurity committees before involving citizen scientists, and make clear which activities must be carried out or supervised by qualified professionals.

3. Plan for inclusion and fairness

Identify groups most affected by environmental or climate implications that may arise through project activities and plan for their proactive inclusion, including vulnerable communities, youth, local experts and under-represented groups that are historically or structurally under-represented in research participation, knowledge production, or decision-making processes relevant to the project domain. Offer diverse participation modes (digital and non-digital, synchronous and asynchronous) and budget for accessibility needs such as language support, interpretation, childcare or travel. Aim to design participation protocols and digital tools (such as apps and platforms) in ways that are accessible, usable, and inclusive across different levels of digital literacy, abilities, and technological access. Anticipate power imbalances and consider structures, such as advisory boards or steering groups, in which citizen scientists participating in the research can influence design, governance, and communication.

4. Fieldwork in natural landscapes

For field-based projects in natural landscapes, conduct a basic ecological and health-and-safety risk assessment in collaboration with local communities, land managers or park authorities. Agree on a simple code of conduct for fieldwork and communicate it clearly to all citizen scientists and participants before activities begin.

Ethics review, governance and data management

This subsection highlights environmental and climate considerations relevant to ethics review, research governance, and data management in citizen science activities.

1. Ethics review

Where required by national legislation, institutional policy, or disciplinary standards, citizen science projects or project proposals should be submitted to appropriate ethics review or oversight bodies, particularly when personal data, images, sensitive geodata, or information about individuals or communities are collected, or when participants may also be research subjects (for example, in surveys or interviews). Project teams should clearly explain the roles of citizen scientists (e.g. co-researchers, contributors), consent and withdrawal mechanisms (including for long-term platforms), and how vulnerable or marginalised groups, especially those disproportionately affected by environmental or climate impacts, will be protected.

In contexts where formal ethics committees do not routinely review citizen science or non-biomedical research, researchers should seek alternative forms of ethical oversight and guidance, such as consultation with institutional ethics officers, data protection officers (DPOs), or equivalent advisory bodies. Such oversight should consider not only data protection and privacy obligations, but also environmental and climate ethics implications, including risks associated with sensitive ecological data, geolocation information, or community-level environmental knowledge.

Project teams should ensure that submissions are supported by a FAIR²-aligned Data Management Plan (DMP) that is supplemented by explicit measures to identify and mitigate ethical risks, including risks associated with personal, environmental, or geospatial data (such as privacy concerns, sensitive ecological information, or harmful secondary uses).

2. Data management, terms and conditions, and open science

Prepare a Data Management Plan (DMP) that covers data types, quality control, storage, access rights, retention periods, and conditions for open or controlled access. Where relevant, address environmental and climate implications of data use, such as risks linked to sensitive ecological data, locations of endangered species, or information that could unintentionally increase environmental pressures.

²Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

Apply privacy-by-design principles in apps and platforms by working with anonymous data whenever possible, and, where this is not feasible, with pseudonymised data. Limit the collection of personal data to what is strictly necessary, clarify permissions, and make privacy settings simple and accessible. Where pseudonymisation is used, keep re-identification keys separate and securely managed. For sensitive environmental or social data (such as locations of endangered species or informal settlements), consider additional protective measures, including spatial generalisation, restricted-access repositories, or delayed public release, to prevent unintended environmental or social harm.

Ensure that consent, privacy controls and terms of use are visible and understandable, shared with participants before they contribute, and consistent with the DMP and ethics approvals. When designing or using digital tools and platforms (for example, apps, sensors, online portals, AI-supported analysis), allow participants to view their data, change privacy settings and request data deletion. Allow participants to also assess and flag accessibility, potential biases and risks of reinforcing digital divides, and offer alternatives or support where possible.

3. Data ownership, traditional knowledge and benefit-sharing

Before data collection, clarify who will be considered the owner or custodian of different types of data (individual observations, community-level data, aggregated datasets, models, code) and project outputs, and how this will be reflected in licences, access conditions and acknowledgements.

When working with local, Indigenous or traditional knowledge, recognise that this may be held collectively and governed by community norms. Some knowledge should not be made openly available, especially if disclosure could lead to environmental harm, resource extraction, over-exploitation, biopiracy or cultural harm. Discuss and document benefit-sharing arrangements with relevant communities and partners, such as access to data and tools, capacity-building, co-authorship or co-branding, or (where appropriate) participation in financial benefits from commercial uses of results.

Information sheets, consent materials and terms and conditions should explain what claims researchers, institutions and third parties may make over data and

knowledge, what claims citizen scientists and communities may retain, and how disputes will be handled (especially when data relate to land, natural resources or environmental stewardship).

Working with citizen scientists in practice

This subsection addresses environmental and climate considerations that may arise during the practical implementation of citizen science activities.

1. Informed consent and information

Provide layered information (a short overview plus a more detailed description) in plain language. Explain the project's purpose, methods, environmental risks and benefits, and how data and metadata will flow and be shared (including open-science aspects and whether data relate to local ecosystems, climate vulnerabilities, or sensitive ecological locations). Where relevant, explicitly address the collection and use of visual data (such as photographs, videos, images, maps, or other visual records).

Clarify how individual participants can withdraw and what happens to existing data, including whether data may be reused in future research, shared with third parties, or combined with other datasets, and under what conditions.

Where research activities affect communities, territories, or shared environmental resources, consider whether additional forms of community-level information, consultation, or consent are appropriate. In some contexts, this may include engagement with community representatives, leaders, or governance bodies before individual participation begins, particularly where research relates to land, natural resources, environmental monitoring, or collective climate vulnerabilities.

2. Avoid undue inducement and ensure voluntary participation

Offer recognition and modest incentives where appropriate (such as reimbursement of expenses, certificates or training) but avoid financial or material benefits that may pressure individuals or communities to participate especially in contexts where environmental or climate vulnerabilities may heighten dependence on such incentives. Make it clear, in writing and verbally, that participation is voluntary and that declining or withdrawing will not affect access to services, support or future collaboration.

3. Training, support and safety³

Provide initial and, where needed, ongoing training for citizen scientists covering data collection protocols and quality standards, use of equipment and digital tools, and safety procedures and environmental rules (e.g. how to minimise ecological impact). Training should also address research integrity and ethics, including responsible conduct, respectful engagement with communities and environments, and personal data management where applicable. Establish clear channels for support and conduct a basic risk assessment for fieldwork that addresses health (including psychological support), safety (including using equipment) and potential environmental impacts for both researchers and citizen scientists.

4. Recognition, feedback and decision-making involvement

Develop a transparent recognition plan that includes acknowledgement of data contributions, appropriate attribution of individual or collective inputs, and clear criteria for co-authorship, where relevant. Recognition may take different forms depending on the level and nature of contribution (e.g. acknowledgements, contributor lists, dataset citations, co-authorship, or public recognition), and should be communicated clearly from the outset.

Provide regular feedback through dashboards, maps, short updates, or co-interpretation sessions, highlighting where environmental or climate-related findings may have implications for local communities or ecosystems.

Where suitable, involve citizen scientists in decisions about project design and priorities, data governance and access rules, and communication formats, especially when data relate to land, resources, environmental monitoring, or climate vulnerabilities.

This helps reduce power imbalances, strengthen trust, and avoid instrumentalising participants solely as data collectors.

5. Conflicts of interest and transparency

Identify and manage conflicts of interest for both professional researchers and citizen scientists, including financial and non-financial interests. Ask team members and citizen scientists in governance or decision-making roles to disclose relevant interests at project start and when circumstances change.

Particular attention should be paid to non-financial conflicts of interest, which may be less visible but can significantly influence research processes and outcomes. These may include strong personal, political, community, advocacy, or professional commitments related to the research topic, local environmental disputes, land or resource use, or anticipated policy outcomes. Project teams should raise awareness of such conflicts, facilitate reflection among participants, and provide clear guidance and examples to help identify them.

Decide how to handle disclosed conflicts in a proportionate manner, for example, by documenting them transparently, using balanced or diverse panels, clarifying roles, or avoiding situations where individuals with strong stakes are solely responsible for critical measurements, interpretation, or communication. Be transparent with participants and stakeholders about funding sources, institutional partnerships, and policy links, especially where these may raise questions about conflicts of interest, independence, advocacy, or industry influence.

³Citizen science raises specific ethical responsibilities with regard to research quality. Researchers should not assume that citizen scientists have prior methodological expertise. Adequate training, clear protocols, and ongoing support are essential to ensure data quality while respecting participants as collaborators rather than shifting responsibility or blame for methodological shortcomings onto them.

Evaluation, learning and long-term stewardship

This subsection highlights environmental and climate considerations relevant to the evaluation of activities, learning processes, and the long-term responsibilities associated with citizen science research.

1. Evaluation

Plan evaluation that covers scientific quality, participant experience (e.g. motivation, perceived respect, learning), ethical performance, and the environmental and social impacts of project activities. Where appropriate, use measurable and transparent indicators to support evaluation, for example indicators related to data quality and reuse, inclusiveness and fairness of participation, handling of ethical incidents or DNSH concerns, and observed environmental or climate-related outcomes of the project.

2. Oversight and long-term stewardship

Document lessons learned and integrate them into institutional policies for citizen science, future project design, and training or micro-modules on research ethics and integrity.

For citizen science projects with long-term monitoring objectives, identify appropriate oversight institutions (e.g., public agencies, trusted repositories, community organisations or RPOs) that can advocate for the interests of all stakeholders. Develop a realistic transition plan for long-term data and platform stewardship, including open data preservation where compatible with privacy and safety, governance arrangements for ongoing access and use, and responsibilities and resources after project funding ends.

Checklist for researchers

Planning

- DNSH and environmental/social risks have been considered and mitigated.
- Potential environmental or climate implications of activities or data uses have been assessed and mitigated.
- Members of the research team as well as citizens (especially those new to citizen science) have received or will receive training on research ethics and integrity related to citizen science practice, and relevant climate/environmental and DNSH considerations.
- Risks of shifting environmental burdens or social risks to other regions (including outside the EU) have been considered (e.g., for field-based or supply-chain-related projects). These have been communicated to citizen scientists and addressed (with the research team and partners) in the impact assessment.
- Clear objectives and a documented rationale for using citizen science are defined and communicated in a form accessible to participants.
- Roles and tasks of citizen scientists are specified.
- For field-based projects (i.e., in natural landscapes), we have conducted an ecological and health-and-safety risk assessment in collaboration with land managers or park authorities, and we have clearly communicated the agreed code of conduct to all citizen scientists.
- Where relevant, health/life science and biosecurity requirements are addressed.
- Inclusion and accessibility needs are identified and resourced.
- Ethics review has been sought where required.
- A Data Management Plan (DMP) exists and covers citizen science data.
- Participants will receive clear terms and conditions consistent with the DMP.
- A risk-tier has been assigned and documented.
- A complaint mechanism exists.

Implementation

- Plain-language information and consent materials are ready.
- Training materials and sessions for citizen scientists are in place.
- Support and communication channels are established.
- Recognition, feedback, and participation-in-decision-making strategies are agreed upon within the team.
- Privacy-by-design measures are implemented in apps/platforms.
- Digital tools and platforms (e.g. apps, sensors, online portals, AI-supported analysis) are assessed not only for privacy/security but also for accessibility, potential biases, and risk of reinforcing digital divides; alternatives or support are offered where needed/possible.
- Safety and environmental rules are communicated and monitored.

Monitoring and evaluation

- Evaluation covers scientific, ethical, environmental and social dimensions.
- Red flags are actively monitored and addressed (e.g., citizen or community concerns that the research project might worsen climate vulnerabilities are not taken seriously or investigated transparently).
- Findings and data are shared in line with consent, terms & conditions, and the DMP.
- Citizen scientists receive accessible feedback on results and impacts.
- Where feasible, results are published in reputable open-access journals or repositories, avoiding predatory outlets that lack transparent peer review and clear editorial standards.
- Lessons learned feed into institutional and project-level improvements.
- Oversight institutions and long-term stewardship plans are identified for ongoing initiatives.

Questions to ask yourself (for researchers)

- Would I still consider this project ethical and fair if I were a citizen scientist participant rather than a professional researcher?
- Are citizen scientists adequately recognised, credited, and acknowledged in ways that reflect the nature and level of their contributions?
- Are citizen scientists genuinely able to opt out without losing essential benefits, access or trust?
- Have we done enough to minimise environmental and social harms associated with our activities and data uses?
- Are those most affected by climate and environmental issues meaningfully included and heard in this project?
- Does our design reflect the core principles of research integrity (reliability, honesty, respect, accountability) in a citizen science context?
- Have we done enough to maximise accessibility and minimise privacy risks associated with our activities, tools, and data practices?
- Have we identified appropriate ethics review, oversight institutions and long-term data preservation arrangements for this project?
- Are we confident that our citizen science project contributes to a just green and digital transition, that is, it prevents significant environmental harms and inequalities rather than simply relocating them in time, space, or to less visible communities?

The consortium

TAKING PART IN RESEARCH: A GUIDE FOR CITIZEN SCIENTISTS ON ENVIRONMENTAL AND CLIMATE CONSIDERATIONS

Executive Summary

This guide is for citizen scientists taking part in research that may have environmental or climate implications, including projects linked to the European Green Deal¹. This means being actively involved in activities such as collecting data, interpreting results, or contributing to project decisions. This guide is designed to help you participate responsibly, understand how your contributions support environmental and climate knowledge and the Do No Significant Harm (DNSH)² principle, and avoid actions that could unintentionally cause environmental or social harm.

At a glance, this guide helps you understand:

- Your rights as a citizen scientist, including receiving clear information, choosing whether to take part, and stopping your participation at any time
- Your responsibilities, such as following project instructions, acting honestly and carefully when collecting or sharing data, and respecting the environment and others involved
- How your participation can support research that is respectful to the environment and climate and contributes to positive outcomes for communities and ecosystems

For quick use, readers may start with the Checklist for Citizen Scientists and the Questions to Ask Yourself, which provide a simple way to reflect on participation and identify potential concerns, and then consult the relevant sections as needed.

Your contribution to research is valuable and should always take place in ways that are safe, transparent, respectful, and ethically sound. In some projects, especially in health and life sciences or where biosecurity considerations are relevant, additional safeguards and requirements may apply. The project team should explain these clearly before you decide whether to participate, and you should feel free to ask questions or seek clarification if anything is unclear.

Before you join: understand the project

1. Project purpose and who is behind it

You should receive a clear, short description of the project's aims (for example, monitoring local heat islands or tracking biodiversity change), who coordinates the project (institutions), who funds it, and how the results are expected to be used (e.g. informing local policies, contributing to scientific publications, supporting environmental management). This information should be provided in accessible, non-technical language. Where relevant, the project should also explain whether its activities or results could create environmental or social impacts beyond the immediate study context, including effects on other communities or future generations, and what measures are taken to minimise such risks.

2. Your role as a citizen scientist

The project should explain clearly what you will do, such as making observations, uploading photos or sensor data, joining workshops, or helping interpret results, including activities that may involve natural areas or environmental data.

¹The European Green Deal is the European Union's comprehensive growth strategy launched in 2019, aiming to transform the EU into a modern, resource-efficient, and competitive economy. Its central goal is to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050, with an interim target to reduce net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030. The framework covers energy, industry, agriculture, transport, and biodiversity to create a sustainable, inclusive, and clean, green transition.

²Do No Significant Harm" (DNSH) is a European Commission principle ensuring investments, particularly under the Recovery and Resilience Facility, do not cause significant environmental damage. It requires projects to meet criteria across six objectives, including climate change mitigation, adaptation, water protection, circular economy, pollution control, and biodiversity.

You are free to decide what level of involvement is realistic for you, and you are not obliged to take on tasks beyond what you agreed at the start. You can also adjust your level of involvement over time or decide to stop at any time.

3. What happens with the data you contribute

The project should explain which types of data will be collected including, where relevant, data that may be collected about you and data that you will collect or generate through your participation (for example dates, locations, measurements, photos, and any environmental or climate-related information you might gather). You should be informed on how to ask questions and feel comfortable asking them if anything is unclear. You should know where and for how long the data you will provide will be stored, how it will be protected and whether it will be openly available or shared under conditions. You should also know how you will receive feedback on results (e.g. maps, dashboards, newsletters or meetings). You should feel comfortable asking questions if anything is unclear.

4. Terms, conditions and duration

You should receive clear terms and conditions that explain how you can participate, how the data you contribute can be used, shared or reused, under which licence, and how long the project and its data infrastructure are expected to run. You should have an opportunity to read these and ask questions before you decide whether they are acceptable to you.

Your rights as a citizen scientist

1. Voluntary participation and right to withdraw

Participation is entirely voluntary. You may decline to participate or withdraw at any time, without penalty. The project should tell you how to withdraw and what will happen to the data you have already contributed including community, environmental or climate-related data.

2. Informed consent

Before you start, you should receive a clear explanation of the project and your role, information on possible environmental benefits and risks, and a consent form (paper or digital) in understandable language. You should confirm consent only if you feel you understand what is involved. In some projects, especially in health and life sciences, additional institutional or regulatory approvals and safety rules may apply. These should also be explained.

3. Privacy and confidentiality

Privacy and confidentiality are especially important when research involves data that may indirectly reveal information about you, such as location data, observations linked to specific places, or contributions associated with identifiable individuals. This may be particularly relevant when datasets include sensitive environmental information (for example, endangered species locations, community sites, or places associated with participants).

4. Recognition and feedback

Your contribution should be acknowledged appropriately (for example in project reports, websites, or publications). You should be able to choose whether to be named or remain anonymous. The project should share results in accessible formats, such as summaries, visuals or public events, and explain how you and other participants contributed to the research (e.g., how your contributions helped advance environmental or climate understanding).

5. Involvement in decisions

Where suitable, you may be invited to help shape decisions about how data are collected and interpreted, how results are communicated, or how data are shared or reused. You are free to accept or decline these roles. Saying no should not affect your participation in the project.

6. Your knowledge, community data and benefit-sharing

If you provide local, environmental, cultural or traditional ecological knowledge to the project team, you have the right to ask how this knowledge will be used, stored and shared, whether your community or group will be recognised as a custodian of this knowledge, and what benefits are planned for you and your community if the research leads to applications or products.

You can decline to share knowledge that you or your community consider sensitive, sacred or vulnerable to misuse. Where knowledge is shared collectively, it may be important that consent and benefit-sharing are discussed at the community level, not only individually.

Your responsibilities as a citizen scientist

1. Act with honesty and care in data collection

Follow the project's instructions and protocols as closely as possible. You should not invent, alter, or selectively report observations. Inform the project team if you are unsure or may have made a mistake. These practices are an essential part of research integrity, which means producing trustworthy knowledge through honest and careful work.

Key integrity issues to keep in mind include fabrication (making up data), falsification (changing or omitting data to influence results), and selective reporting (only sharing results that support a preferred outcome). Noting uncertainties, limitations, or unexpected results is part of good research practice, especially when environmental or climate-related data may inform local decisions or policies.

You should also be aware that strong personal, professional, or community interests related to the research topic can unintentionally influence how data are collected or interpreted. Being open about such interests and following agreed protocols helps ensure that the research remains fair, credible, and useful to others.

2. Respect people's privacy

You should avoid capturing identifiable images or information about people (for example faces, license plates, house numbers) and avoid sharing other participants' personal information without consent. You should take care when posting project-related screenshots or maps on social media especially if they show sensitive environmental or location data.

3. Respect nature and local rules (Do No Significant Harm)

You should follow rules for protected areas and natural sites, including "[leave no trace](#)" principles, staying on marked paths where advised, avoiding disturbing wildlife (especially during breeding seasons), and following any biosecurity instructions such as cleaning boots to avoid spreading invasive species. You should also ensure your activities do not inadvertently block access to public spaces for others or create local nuisances (noise/light) while monitoring.

Non-personal environmental data (for example, animal behaviour, species presence, weather, water levels) should be gathered in the least intrusive way possible, avoiding disturbance, stress, injury or damage to animals and habitats. EU and national

rules on the ethical treatment of animals also apply when research is carried out by citizen scientists. If a protocol ever feels harmful or inappropriate for animals, you should stop and contact the project team for clarification.

You should not collect samples (such as plants, animals, soil) without explicit instructions and you should always respect local regulations and conservation rules. Take litter away and minimise your environmental footprint during field activities (e.g. choosing a sustainable mode of transport to reach sampling sites where possible).

4. Use technology responsibly

You should use only the official apps or tools provided by the project, keep your accounts and devices secure (for example, by using passwords and updates), and report technical problems such as GPS errors or app bugs to the project team. This is particularly important when your device collects location or environmental data that might be sensitive.

5. Support, inclusion and respect

You should treat other participants and community members with respect, welcome newcomers, and value different kinds of knowledge (local, Indigenous, expert, lay). Inclusive and respectful participation strengthens environmental and climate research and ensures diverse perspectives are represented. Report to the project team any harassment or discrimination you experience or observe.

6. Be open about your interests and roles

If you or your organisation have strong interests related to the project topic (for example employment in a company, NGO or public authority involved in the issue, or a role in a campaign or court case), you should tell the project team. This does not disqualify you from taking part; it helps avoid misunderstandings and supports fair interpretation of data especially when environmental or climate issues affect different groups differently.

Checklist for citizen scientists

Before joining

- I understand what the project is about and who is organising it.
- I know what my role will be and how often I am expected to contribute.
- I have read or received an explanation of how the data I will provide will be used, stored and shared.
- I have seen the terms and conditions and know how long the project is expected to run.
- I know how to ask questions and how to withdraw if I change my mind.
- I understand whether the project has environmental or climate implications and how my contribution supports fair and sustainable outcomes.
- I have been told how the project aims to avoid shifting environmental or social harms to other communities (including outside the EU) or future generations.
- I know I will receive a short introduction or training on collecting data, protecting privacy, and minimising environmental impacts.

While participating

- I follow the agreed protocols and ask for help when unsure.
- I respect privacy, nature and local rules.
- I record uncertainties or mistakes instead of hiding them.
- I use project tools responsibly and keep my account secure.
- If I feel unsafe or uncomfortable due to the behaviour of others, I know how to report this and trust that my concerns will be taken seriously.
- If I notice potential harm to nature or unintended impacts on certain groups, such as increased exposure to climate or environmental risks, I know how to raise this with the project team and expect them to respond promptly and transparently to my concerns.

After contributing

- I stay informed about how results and findings are communicated, including whether sensitive environmental or climate-related data are handled responsibly.
- I speak up if I see potential harm, misuse of data, or risks for communities or ecosystems.
- I make use of opportunities to learn from the results (e.g., meetings, dashboards, summaries) and understand how my contribution supports environmental or climate objectives.

Questions to ask yourself

- Do I feel free to say no or to stop participating if I want to?
- Do I trust the organisations running this project to use the data I contribute responsibly?
- Am I comfortable with how my personal data and location information are handled?
- Do I understand how my contribution can help address climate and environmental challenges?
- Is my participation respectful of nature, local communities, and my own wellbeing?
- If I am invited into decision-making (e.g. about data use or communication), do I feel that my voice is genuinely listened to?
- Does this project explain who benefits from the results and who might bear any environmental costs or risks, both locally and in other places that may be affected, including longer-term environmental or societal impacts?

If your answer to one or several of these questions is "no" or "not sure," consider discussing your concerns with the project team or seeking clarification before continuing your participation.

The consortium

UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE.

